

Supplier Performance: Evaluating the Importance of Intangible and Tangible Factors within the Purchaser–Supplier Relationship

Andrew Bell, MBA (Distinction)

Sponsored by: Chartered Institute of Purchasing & Supply (CIPS)

Supervised by: Brian Jeffery (Coventry University)

Research team: Andrew Bell, Brian Jeffery, Carl Kochelbergh

Thesis submitted: 31 August 1999

Supplier Performance: Evaluating the Importance
of
Intangible and Tangible Factors
within the
Purchaser - Supplier Relationship

Master of Business Administration
Coventry University

Thesis - 1999

Andrew Bell

31 August 1999

Supplier Performance: Evaluating the Importance
of
Intangible and Tangible Factors
within the
Purchaser - Supplier Relationship

Summary

Why do organisations do business with their current suppliers? Why do they stay with suppliers and why do they sometimes cease to do business with a particular supplier? What were the events that finally led to the supplier being de-listed? For a given company, as these questions are answered, it will soon become apparent whether there is a supplier performance measurement system in place. Conventional wisdom suggests that setting standards and then measuring performance against those standards is the starting point if business systems are to be improved. The purchasing systems, linking the company to the outside world, lie at the heart of the system that is the business itself. Supplier performance is in many ways dependent on purchasing performance and certainly impacts on the company's performance

Initial research has shown that with supplier performance measurement the actual processes used within industry and the service sector are based largely around given quantifiable factors. Goffin found in a 1997 study of supplier base reduction that "Most of the criteria for supplier choice are focused on quantifiable measures; however, other more qualitative factors need to be considered. For example, an assessment needs to be made of whether the culture of the supplier's organisation can co-operate effectively with the buyer's organisational culture.". This applies even to large scale pieces of research work such as the 'BRAVO' benchmarking study carried out in the Netherlands.

The quantifiable factors are often judged on a speculative scoring basis by staff within the purchasers organisation. This whilst obviously being subject to operator bias requires a historical perspective on the relationship. The speculative score based systems are not appropriate for benchmarking suppliers and relatively little literature exists on this subject.

This thesis details plans to investigate the current state of supplier performance evaluation and also to determine the extent to which the intangible and tangible elements of the supply relationship interact and affect the ease of business with the supplier.

The objective of the thesis is to establish the relevance and importance of the intangible factors that influence the Supplier/Customer relationship and impact on Supplier performance as it is normally measured using tangible evidence.

The Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply receive many calls a month about evaluating suppliers and measuring their performance. In response to members needs, in this area of professional practice, the Institute in partnership with Coventry University Business School has initiated this research in this very important area. The thesis is based on an analysis of current practice, leading edge thinking, and the output from two focus groups plus a 2,500 CIPS member company targeted survey.

The thesis aims to support and investigate four central hypotheses,

- H-1. Physical aspects of the supply chain such as delivery performance, price and quality whilst being vital to good manufacturing and service provision are given factors and are not responsible for the perceived ease of business with the supplier, and the success of the supply

relationship.

- H-2. The formal contract, and tangible procedures such as TQM, as a form of physical measurement have little impact on the ease of business and the success of the supply relationship.
- H-3. Purchaser confidence in, and acknowledgement of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier, the interaction between the parties and the confidence in the information received is directly related to the perceived ease of the supply relationship.
- H-4. The frequency of interaction between the purchaser and supplier does not directly impinge on the ease of business, but rather it is the quality of interaction that increases the ease of business and the potential success of the supply relationship

The report concluded that conformance to procedure and specification has little impact on the perceived ease of business with the suppliers. This does not mean to say that if these physical factors were uncontrolled that the ease of business relations would be unaffected, but that this element of the business relationship is well within the control of the purchasing professionals

Physical aspects of the supply chain such as delivery performance, price and quality whilst being vital to good manufacturing and service provision are given factors and are not responsible for the perceived ease of business with the supplier, and the success of the supply relationship.

The formal contract had no discernible impact on the purchasing professionals perception of the ease of business with the supplier. This would suggest that whilst the formal contract is a record of the agreement and a measure of the physical properties of supply, it does not, as a continual metric of that supply increase the ease of the business

relationship, nor does it increase the chance of success of the supply relationship. In fact a reliance on the supply contract as a formal measure may well decrease the effectiveness and ease of the supplier purchaser relationship in that it may well reduce the real interaction between the two groups to an adversarial set of measures and contract waving.

This and the findings from the questionnaire support the second hypothesis of this thesis that, **the formal contract, and tangible procedures such as TQM, as a form of physical measurement have little impact on the ease of business and the success of the supply relationship.**

By having confidence in the skills and knowledge base of the supplier the organisation is able to work with that supplier, the survey shows that there is a high degree of correlation at operational, tactical and strategic levels relating to the degree of confidence , and the perception of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier with the perceived ease of transaction and business.

This relates to the skills and knowledge grid as proposed earlier in this thesis, the grid directly relates the balance of power between the two organisations, purchaser and supplier.

Purchaser confidence in, and acknowledgement of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier, the interaction between the parties and the confidence in the information received is directly related to the perceived ease of the supply relationship.

The data analysis shows that with a TQM programme in place and a reported high level of interaction between the supplier and the purchaser that the perceived ease of business increases, this is also true for companies that operate joint multidisciplinary teams. However the data showed that the frequency of these meetings has little impact on the perceived ease of the business relationship.

it is the quality of the communication and the inter personal relations that build up through inter-organisational contact that is responsible for the increased incidence of successful supply / purchaser relations.

The frequency of interaction between the purchaser and supplier does not directly impinge on the ease of business, but rather it is the quality of interaction that increases the ease of business and the potential success of the supply relationship.

Andrew Bell

31st August 1999

1.	Introduction	1
2.	Aims and Objectives	3
3.	Literature Summary.....	5
4.	Research Methods	18
5.	Data Analysis	19
6.	Synthesis.....	20
7.	Findings, Analysis and Discussion.....	21
7.1.	Phase 1: Defining the Current State	21
7.2.	Phase 2: The Supply Chain –Value: Tangible and	27
7.3.	Phase 3: The Purchasing Function – Roles and Responsibilities.....	31
7.4.	Phase 4: The Focus Groups: Defining the Themes	34
7.5.	Phase 5: Questionnaire and Outcomes	43
7.6.	Phase 6: Analysis of Questionnaire	45
7.6.1.	Basic Company Information	46
7.6.2.	Expectations of Suppliers: The Tangibles	60
7.6.3.	Expectations of Suppliers: The Intangibles	70
7.6.4.	Expectation of Suppliers: Information.....	85
7.6.5.	Expectation of Supplier: Working with the Supplier.....	91
7.7.	Hypotheses	98
7.7.1.	H-1: The Relevance of Physical Aspects of Supply to the Success of the Supply Relationship and the Ease of Business.....	99
7.7.2.	H-2: The Impact of the Formal Contract and Tangible Procedures as a Form of Physical Measurement ,on the Supply Relationship	105
7.7.3.	H-3: The Ease of Relationship as Directly Related to the Skills and Knowledge Base of the Supplier	109
7.7.4.	H-4: The Impact of the Frequency and Quality of Interaction Between the Purchaser and Supplier on the Ease of Business.....	114
8.	Conclusions & Reccomendations	116
9.	References.....	119

Figure 1: Complex Supply Chain Model	22
Figure 2: Number of Employees	47
Figure 3: Numbers within the Purchasing Department.....	48
Figure 4: Industrial Sector.....	49
Figure 5: Mission Critical Purchasing Area.....	50
Figure 6: Subsidiary Purchasing Areas	51
Figure 7: Overall Our Suppliers Meet the Delivery Standards we Expect	61
Figure 8: Overall Our Suppliers meet the Product / Service Standards we Expect.....	62
Figure 9: Overall Our Suppliers Meet the Price Performance Targets we Expect.....	63
Figure 10: Importance of the Skills Base of Suppliers: Operational, Tactical and Strategic Level.....	71
Figure 11: Confidence in the Skills Base of Suppliers: Operational, Tactical and Strategic Level.....	72
Figure 12: The Perception of the Supplier Knowledge Base as an Important Component of the Business Relationship at the Operational, Tactical and Strategic Level	78
Figure 13: Purchaser Confidence in the Knowledge Base of the Supplier at the Operational, Tactical and Strategic Levels.....	79
Figure 14: Confidence in Information Received from Suppliers.....	87
Figure 15: Confidence in Internal Information	87
Figure 16: Confidence in Internal and Supplier Generated Information.....	89
Figure 17: Extent of Interaction with Mission Critical Suppliers	92
Figure 18: Frequency of Joint Meetings with Suppliers for Organisations Operating Multidisciplinary Teams	94

Table 1: Average Annual Spend on Mission Critical Items	52
Table 2: Total Employed / Purchasing Employed	53
Table 3: Cross Tabulation of Basic Purchasing Information	54
Table 4: Industry Type Cross-Tabulated against Mission Critical Purchasing Area	56
Table 5: Industry Type Cross Tabulated against Subsidiary Purchasing Areas	56
Table 6: Spend Cross tabulated against Industry Type and Mission Critical Purchasing Area	57
Table 7: Expected Delivery Performance Cross-Tabulated against Expected Price.....	65
Table 8: Expected Product / Service Quality Cross-Tabulated against Price	66
Table 9: Expected Delivery Standards Cross-Tabulated against Product Quality.....	67
Table 10: Cross-Tabulation Importance / Confidence: Skills base of Suppliers at all Levels.....	73
Table 11: Cross-Tabulation: Tactical Importance / Confidence: Skills base of Suppliers at all Levels.....	74
Table 12: Cross-Tabulation Strategic Importance / Confidence: Skills base of Suppliers at all Levels.....	75
Table 13: Skew of Response to the Importance of the Suppliers Skills Base	76
Table 14: Skew of Response to the Confidence in the Suppliers Skills Base	76
Table 15: Cross-Tabulation Operational Importance / Confidence: Knowledge Base of Suppliers at all Levels	80
Table 16: Cross-Tabulation Tactical Importance / Confidence: Knowledge Base of Suppliers at all Levels	81
Table 17: Cross-Tabulation: Strategic Importance / Confidence: Knowledge Base of Suppliers at all Levels	82
Table 18: Skew of Response to the Confidence in the Suppliers Skills Base	83
Table 19: Skew of Response to the Confidence in the Suppliers Skills Base	83
Table 20: Cross-Tabulation of Confidence in Supplier and Purchaser Internal Information.....	88

Table 21: Interaction in the 46.3 % of Organisations Not Operating a TQM Programme	93
Table 22: Supplier Interaction in the 53.8 % of Organisations Operating a TQM Programme	93
Table 23: Perception of Ease of Business With Suppliers Dependant on the Existence of a TQM Programme	93
Table 24: Perceived Ease of Business with Suppliers Compared to the Existence of Multidisciplinary Teams and TQM Programmes	95
Table 25: Perceived Ease of Business with Suppliers Compared to the Existence of Multidisciplinary Teams But No TQM Programmes	95
Table 26: The Use of the Formal Contract for Measuring Performance	97
Table 27: Ease of Business and the Use of the Formal Contract as a Means of Measuring Performance	97

Appendix 1: Lawrence and Galati's Four Pillars.....	126
Appendix 2: The Questionnaire	128
Appendix 3: Cross Tabulation of Skills and Knowledge Data	137
Appendix 4: Synthesis Report from Focus Group Meetings	139
Appendix 5: Stevens Four Stages in the Evolutionary Process of Restructuring	143
Appendix 6: 1 st Focus Group Report	145
Appendix 7: 2 nd Focus Group Meeting Report	147

Supplier Performance: Evaluating the Importance of
Intangible and Tangible Factors within the Purchaser / Supplier
Relationship

1. Introduction

Why do organisations do business with their current suppliers? Why do they stay with suppliers and why do they sometimes cease to do business with a particular supplier? What were the events that finally led to the supplier being de-listed? For a given company, as these questions are answered, it will soon become apparent whether there is a supplier performance measurement system in place. Conventional wisdom suggests that setting standards and then measuring performance against those standards is the starting point if business systems are to be improved. The purchasing systems, linking the company to the outside world, lie at the heart of the system that is the business itself. Supplier performance is in many ways dependent on purchasing performance and certainly impacts on the company's performance

Initial research has shown that with supplier performance measurement the actual processes used within industry and the service sector are based largely around given quantifiable factors. Goffin¹ found in a 1997 study of supplier base reduction that "Most of the criteria for supplier choice are focused on quantifiable measures; however, other more qualitative factors need to be considered. For example, an assessment needs to be made of whether the culture of the supplier's organisation can co-operate effectively with the buyer's organisational culture.²". This applies even to large scale pieces of research work such as the 'BRAVO' benchmarking study carried out in the Netherlands³.

The quantifiable factors are often judged on a speculative scoring basis by staff within the purchasers organisation. This whilst obviously being

subject to operator bias requires a historical perspective on the relationship. The speculative score based systems are not appropriate for benchmarking suppliers and relatively little literature exists on this subject.

This thesis details plans to investigate the current state of supplier performance evaluation and also to determine the extent to which the intangible and tangible elements of the supply relationship interact and affect the ease of business with the supplier.

2. Aims and Objectives

The objective of the thesis is to establish the relevance and importance of the intangible factors that influence the Supplier/Customer relationship and impact on Supplier performance as it is normally measured using tangible evidence.

The Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply receive many calls a month about evaluating suppliers and measuring their performance. In response to members needs, in this area of professional practice, the Institute in partnership with Coventry University Business School has initiated this research in this very important area. The thesis is based on an analysis of current practice, leading edge thinking, and the output from two focus groups plus a 2,500 CIPS member company targeted survey.

The thesis aims to support and investigate four central hypotheses,

- H-1. Physical aspects of the supply chain such as delivery performance, price and quality whilst being vital to good manufacturing and service provision are given factors and are not responsible for the perceived ease of business with the supplier, and the success of the supply relationship.
- H-2. The formal contract, and tangible procedures such as TQM, as a form of physical measurement have little impact on the ease of business and the success of the supply relationship.
- H-3. Purchaser confidence in, and acknowledgement of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier, the interaction between the parties and the confidence in the information received is directly related to the perceived ease of the supply relationship.

H-4. The frequency of interaction between the purchaser and supplier does not directly impinge on the ease of business, but rather it is the quality of interaction that increases the ease of business and the potential success of the supply relationship

3. Literature Summary

Details of the literature & journals studied during the completion of this thesis is contained in this section, a review of this literature with abstracts and its significance to the six initial phases of this work is detailed below.

- International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Feb 1996 v26 n2 p4(19)
Role of benchmarking as a competitive strategy: the logistics experience.
Prabir K. Bagchi.

Abstract: More companies are using benchmarking as a tool for their business process reengineering efforts, particularly in logistics operations. Benchmarking helps businesses identify key elements that can help them gain a competitive edge in the marketplace. The success of benchmarking depends heavily on the identification and understanding of an organization's internal processes and the education of management and employees regarding the benchmarking process and its aims.

- Management Today, Jan 1996 p56(5)
To beat the best. (benchmarking)
Anita Van de Vliet.

Abstract: UK and European companies were often latecomers to benchmarking and total quality management, but are now using many techniques, including internal benchmarking. Consultants Sylvia Codling of Oak Business Developers and Graham Hoenes of

Benchmarking Centre describe their practices.

- Personnel Journal, Nov 1995 v74 n11 p62(10)
Discover best practices through benchmarking
Samuel Greengard.

Abstract: Intense competition and the consequent demand to produce more with less resources are driving many human resource managers to turn to benchmarking to empower employees and increase productivity. Benchmarking entails the study of the best practices of other companies and then implementing those best practices in one's own company. It also means measuring a company's performance, and then comparing it with industry performance. Goodyear Tire and Rubber Co. and Xerox Corp. are two companies that are extensively using benchmarking, particularly in human resource management.

- Management Accounting (British), Sept 1995 v73 n8 p26(2)
Strategic alliance with suppliers and its rewards in the accounts payable process
Ian Malcolm.

Abstract: Financial services benchmarking has the potential to reduce costs and improve performance. Benchmarking the performances of finance functions, such as accounts payable and transaction processing, can reveal where inefficiencies occur. Closer partnerships between finance departments and strategic alliances with suppliers can result in improved accounts payable performance and a move nearer to global best practice as detailed in Arthur Andersen's Global Best Practices Knowledge Base.

- Journal of Managerial Psychology, June 1995 v10 n6 p41(7)
Self-assessment and benchmarking product development in five Irish firms.

Paul Coughlan; Emer Brady.

Abstract: A research was conducted using a combined self-assessment and benchmarking approach to improve the management of product development process in five Irish firms. The approach employed three generic phases: action research and initial assessment; sharing of data and observations within and between the firms; and development and discussion of action plans. Through a comparative analyses of the process, benchmarks were recognized and gaps in the practice were identified.

- Management Review, June 1995 v84 n6 p39(5)
Benchmarking: people make the process.

Charles Goldwasser.

Abstract: It is difficult for benchmarking to be effective unless specific goals are articulated before the process begins. A visit to another company should be planned thoroughly in advance, so that important questions can be asked and answered in the field. A way to assemble the data is essential in order to convince others that the results are worth considering. The implementation of the ideas discovered during the visit will need to be done by key personnel who believe in the importance of the research and the changes.

- International Journal of Operations & Production Management, April 1995 v15 n4 p50(13)

The process of benchmarking: a study from the automotive industry.

Rick Delbridge; James Lowe; Nick Oliver.

Abstract: A study on the benchmarking practices of 18 motor vehicle suppliers looked at nine Japanese and nine UK firms to identify the crucial elements for successful benchmarking. The results demonstrate that good benchmarking practices are based on a high level of communications, qualitative research methods, attention to detail and consistency, a 'well-bounded comparison process,' performance measures and participants' knowledge of the process. The study extends the work of the 1985-1990 International Motor Vehicle Program.

- Industry Week, March 15, 1993 v242 n6 p28(4)

Where bench-markers go wrong. (includes an article on hiring consultants)

John H. Sheridan.

Abstract: Businesses employ a number of incorrect practices that make benchmarking unsuccessful, such as failing to align benchmarking with strategic goals. Benchmarking is an important aspect of Total Quality Management.

- Industry Week, March 15, 1993 v242 n6 p46(1)
Capitalizing on comparisons: can benchmarking actually slow you down?

Tom Brown.

Abstract: Bench-marks are beneficial when used in an efficient manner, but they become burdensome if it consumes too much time and paperwork. Bench-marks help to measure and compare performance between companies and reveal better procedures.

- Training, Feb 1993 v30 n2 p36(6)
The limits of benchmarking.

Marc Hequet.

Abstract: Benchmarking does not always work for every company. According to a joint study by Ernst & Young and the American Quality Foundation, benchmarking against the best companies is manifestly beneficial only to high-performing companies. On the other hand, medium and small performers do not receive any significant advantage from benchmarking. The research also discovered that the reason for this is that the lower performers do not possess the quality structure that would facilitate organizational change needed in imitating the best. These companies should exert its efforts on developing cross-functional groups, training employees and relegating control to them, and on improving operations that are strategically important. The necessary measures that need to be taken before benchmarking are also discussed.

- Transportation & Distribution, Oct 1992 v33 n10 p32(4)

Improve quality through benchmarking.

Helen L. Richardson.

Abstract: Benchmarking, according to Xerox's Robert Camp, is finding and implementing the best industrial practices.

Benchmarking programs can be complex and expensive, so it is usually not worthwhile to benchmark company strengths.

Benchmarking teams must be well trained and have the appropriate skills. These teams must meticulously search out the best examples of the functions or processes being benchmarked.

- The Economist, May 11, 1991 v319 n7706 p72(1)

First find your bench

Abstract: this month we look at benchmarking, an increasingly popular way for firms to measure themselves against top corporate performers. Easy in theory, it is tough in practice.

- Total Quality Management, July 1998 v9 n4-5 pS121(5)

Best practice benchmarking: delivering the goods?

(Proceedings of the 3rd World Congress for Total Quality Management Business Excellence Through Quality Culture)

Jacky Holloway; Graham Francis; Matthew Hinton; David Mayle.

Abstract: Benchmarking continues to be an effective means of evaluating quality management. The procedure relies on several factors for accuracy and efficiency, including input from relevant staff in all departments and an understanding of the processes needed to participate. Benchmarking must also be adapted to apply

to the specific organizational context being evaluated.

- Journal of Management, Jan-Feb 1998 v24 n1 p73(24)
A field experiment on the effects of benchmarking and goal setting on company sales performance.
Leon Mann; Danny Samson; Douglas Dow.

Abstract: A field experiment was performed to investigate the effectiveness of internal benchmarking and goal-setting on boosting sales performance. In this study, 130 branches of an Australian electrical wholesale company were designated in random order to any of four conditions. The four conditions were benchmarking, 'small-wins' goal-setting, 'big-bang' goal-setting and control group. Findings revealed that benchmarking produced superior performance, exceeding that achieved through both kinds of goal-setting. Benchmarking is beneficial not only in goal evaluation and goal-setting but also in motivating and disseminating information about best practice.

- International Journal of Operations & Production Management, Sept-Oct 1997 v17 n9-10 p1046(13)
Benchmarking and operational performance: some empirical results.
Christopher A. Voss; Par Ahlstrom; Kate Blackmon.

Abstract: Many organizations have used benchmarking in order to comprehend what practices are needed to meet international operational standards. It is defined as a search for industry's best practices that lead to excellent performance. A research was conducted among 600 European manufacturing sites to indicate the link between benchmarking and operational performance. The

study involves a deeper understanding of the firm's competitive position, its strengths and weaknesses and provides systematic approach for an effective change.

- Management Decision, Sept-Oct 1997 v35 n9-10 p649(3)
Management duckspeak. (meaningless terms used in management)

Stan Glaser.

Abstract: Management concepts are continuously being invented which, if analyzed carefully, are misguided and do not really enhance organizational effectiveness. One such concept is the linkage of shareholder value to corporate strategy. In reality, however, managing for shareholder value is a vague and meaningless theory. Another example is the notion of total quality management (TQM). TQM proponents assert that quality must be managed differently from other management concerns because it is unique. They even promote TQM as the be-all or end-all of management. TQM led to another management terminology that lacks sense, benchmarking. While benchmarking promotes organizational efficiency and competitiveness, it is not a totally novel idea. Other so-called management newspeak are 360 degree feedback and empowerment.

- International Journal of Operations & Production Management, July-August 1997 v17 n7-8 p707(14)

An innovative survey in the transportation and distribution sector. (Survey Research in Operations Management)

Karel van Donselaar; Graham Sharman.

Abstract: An innovative survey, through the BRAVO project at Eindhoven University of Technology in The Netherlands, was conducted to determine the key success factors in the transportation and distribution (T & D) sector. Operational and financial data of 150 T&D companies were then analyzed. Using operation-based segmentation in benchmarking, success factors at three levels, namely, strategic, operational and tactical, were identified.

- Industrial Management & Data Systems, March-April 1997 v97 n3-4 p125(6)

A stage-wise application of total quality management through the product life cycle.

Monica Parzinger; Narender Ramarapu; E. Timmerman.

Abstract: The successful implementation of total quality management (TQM) practices in the workplace is dependent upon implementation factors such as executive commitment, benchmarking, training, open organization, employee empowerment, flexible manufacturing and process improvement. Management practitioners can ensure the success of TQM programs by tying up the said program with product life cycle issues.

- Asian Review of Business and Technology, Oct 1997 p36(3)

Going with the flow. (logistics)

Abstract: Demand Flow Technology (DFT) is important for the Hyster Europe group, which makes forklift trucks. DFT has brought benefits for Hyster Europe and its customers. Logistics and improving supply chain management (SCM) are important for a company that wants to reduce costs and improve services to the level that is needed in the demanding 1997 marketplace. Balancing goals of cost reduction and enhanced customer service can be challenging. Using SCM as a competitive weapon can be too. In Europe, manufacturing is being rationalized.

- Industry Week, Feb 2, 1998 v247 n3 p36(1)

The supply chain's value-add. (reflections on current state of supply chain management in industry)(Editorial)

Doug Bartholomew.

- Grocer, Sep 20, 1997 v220 n7323 pS12(2)

Let's talk about us. (Tesco PLC, relationship with its suppliers)(The Grocer focus on Tesco supplement.)

Christian Cull.

Abstract: The supply chain management of Tesco PLC have been endeavouring to find ways of improving their relationship with supply companies. They have introduced the concept of Efficient Consumer Response (ECR) to cut lead times to around 36 hours. Supply Chain Development Director Graham Booth points out that ECR has reduced the time of stock to sales to 11 days from 22 days. The introduction of home shopping and Express store formats will bring new challenges to the supply network. Cross-docking, to

cut stock levels, is unlikely to be successful due to the infrastructure in the UK.

- International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)
Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more.
Keith Goffin; Marek Szejczewski; Colin New.

Abstract: Several companies are capitalizing on supply chain management as a means for achieving long-term competitive advantage. A study on four sectors on UK industry was conducted to analyze the increasing trend of supplier base reduction. The results indicate that the main reason for supplier base reduction was the need to manage suppliers more effectively. The study further shows the criteria used for supplier selection and the reasons why single-sourcing was avoided.

- International Small Business Journal, April-June 1997 v15 n3 p13(17)
Small firms' training and competitiveness. Building upon the small business as a learning organisation
Allan A. Gibb.

Abstract: Links between the training of small business, its performance and competitiveness are currently being examined in the UK and most of Europe. The search for links has concentrated on investment in training and returns on that investment. The small business as an effective business learning organisation is explored, including ways of adding value to small business learning, with examples of the SME stakeholder environment.

- Harvard Business Review, Nov 1, 1998 p24(1)

Supply Chain Management.

John T. Landry.

Abstract: In a study of Ford Motor Co. and Chrysler Corp. conducted by associate professor Ranjay Galati of Northwestern University's J.L. Kellogg Graduate School of Management and Professor Paul Lawrence of the Harvard Business School, the relationships between these major U.S. manufacturers and their suppliers were examined to determine what constitutes the most efficient and long term alliances. The study concluded that the four major winning points were power balancing, or ensuring that neither company is too dependent on the other; cospecialization, or mutual dependence, such as when a supplier has a factory that makes parts for a particular car model and a carmaker uses one of its assembly lines to fit the needs of a supplier; target costing, which does away with competitive bidding policy by setting target costs based on the manufacturer's car's sale price goal; and personal alliances between managers.

- Industrial Management & Data Systems, March-April 1997 v97 n3-4 p125(6)

A stage-wise application of total quality management through the product life cycle.

Monica Parzinger; Narendra Ramarapu; E. Timmerman.

Abstract: The successful implementation of total quality management (TQM) practices in the workplace is dependent upon implementation factors such as executive commitment, benchmarking, training, open organization, employee empowerment, flexible manufacturing and process improvement.

Management practitioners can ensure the success of TQM programs by tying up the said program with product life cycle issues.

- Journal of Management, Summer 1995 v21 n2 p231(20)
The strategic usefulness of management information as perceived by middle managers.

Mzamo P. Mangaliso.

Abstract: Middle managers were asked to report in a questionnaire what they perceive to be the effect of the contextual variables of decentralization and environmental uncertainty on the strategic role of management information. The respondent middle managers worked for a foreign subsidiary of a large, diversified multinational company. Results showed that the management information characteristics of aggregation, scope and timeliness were significantly related to perceived environmental uncertainty.

4. Research Methods

The work leading up to this thesis involved extensive collaboration between Coventry University, myself and the Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply (CIPS).

Two industry focus groups were formed in order to discuss the rudiments of the hypotheses with senior purchasing practitioners and also to explore areas that would eventually lead to the questions in the survey. The survey was sent to 2,500 CIPS members at a senior level, and received an 11% response.

The questionnaires, mainly using the Likert scale, were then subject to entry using Pinpoint, a statistical analysis tool for questionnaires.

5. Data Analysis

This section will examine the methods employed to analyse the information generated by the initial work and data collection leading to this thesis.

The initial literature review work was analysed through a series of joint meetings between myself , Brian Jeffery of Coventry University and Carl Kochelbergh of the CIPS. This lead to the themes being agreed for the focus group work. Two reports were then written around this work with a following synthesis and review of progress.

The questionnaire was developed over a number of weeks and trialed, the work was revised a number of times before its issue to 2,500 CIPS members in the UK.

The returned data was then collated using Pinpoint and was subject to extensive data analysis in order to underpin the initial hypotheses of this thesis.

6. Synthesis

The conclusions and recommendations will be drawn from the findings by qualitative analysis of the results of each phase of the thesis and the comparison of these findings to the appropriate data from the questionnaire and also the background reading in support of the work.

The results will then be used to test the four central hypotheses of the thesis.

7. Findings, Analysis and Discussion

7.1. Phase 1: Defining the Current State

Why do organisations do business with their current suppliers? Why do they stay with suppliers and why do they sometimes cease to do business with a particular supplier? What were the events that finally led to the supplier being de-listed? For a given company, as these questions are answered, it will soon become apparent whether there is a supplier performance measurement system in place. Conventional wisdom suggests that setting standards and then measuring performance against those standards is the starting point if business systems are to be improved. The purchasing systems, linking the company to the outside world, lie at the heart of the system that is the business itself. Supplier performance is in many ways dependent on purchasing performance and certainly impacts on the company's performance.

For any given product, the supply chain can be defined as a series of activities that are necessary to convert raw materials into a finished good and to make that finished good available to the end-user/consumer. Normally, this series of activities will take place in different companies and changes of ownership will occur as the various stages are completed.

Usual business practices will result in the individual companies in the supply chain making their operations as effective and efficient as possible taking into account a set of given circumstances. These circumstances are the constraints acting upon the company and they are internally and externally generated. The internal constraints are wide ranging covering areas such as:

1. Structure of location of site not ideal

2. Building not ideal, production lines designed to cope with the building layout rather than to obtain optimum flow characteristics
3. Company culture resists change
4. Technology support inadequate

The external constraints are also wide ranging and cover areas such as:

1. Skill shortages in local population
2. Location geographically not ideal
3. Supplier capability
4. Requirements of customers

Figure 1: Complex Supply Chain Model

In adding value terms the total value added by the companies in the supply chain above is the price at which the item is sold to the end user/consumer. Each of the companies have added a certain amount of value and incurred costs in doing so. The difference between the value added by a company and the costs incurred may be represented as profit. Similarly if the whole supply chain is viewed then the total

profit in the chain equals the difference between the final value and all the incurred costs. This suggests that for a given value delivered to the end user/ consumer, the whole supply chain should be optimised to reduce costs whilst maintaining the actual value added. This does not happen! The internal and external constraints that exist at the various stages of the supply chain dilute the effect of this optimisation, and included in these constraints are the differing agendas of the companies in the supply chain. The rationale for partnership type relationships between the companies in a supply chain has as its goal the best possible optimisation of operations and the sharing of profits. The reality in many cases sees an adversarial relationship between customer and supplier, each with their own agenda, making decisions on a company basis whilst trying to force compliance on the other supply chain players. The goal is still the optimisation of the supply chain but the target is a particular company value chain with the additional goal of maximising the profits for that company.

Whichever of the two scenarios the optimisation process looks at, either adversarial or partnership, the processes of all the companies of the supply chain impact on the processes of each other so that the configuration of one company's processes is a limiting factor on the optimisation of the processes in another company. In the absence of a true partnering agreement the opportunity and ability to influence the processes of a supplier both operational and managerial will be important.

In examining improvements in supplier performance benchmarking it is imperative to assess methodology already in place within industry sectors, as Van de Vliet⁴ observed

Once you've chosen your process for improvement, the first task is to analyse current practice - to examine the process from start to finish; the assessment of processes, if done at all, is frequently done in a very fragmented way.

A large proportion of Supplier / Purchaser relationships can be judged to be unsatisfactory in some fundamental aspect. A recent editorial in 'Industry Week' ⁵ showed that, "In a 1997 survey of IS executives by Computer Sciences Corp, the supply chain was the fifth most important issue, up from 16th just three years ago". The same editorial also stated that

....there's plenty of opportunity, especially when it comes to partnerships. Two or three companies working together can obtain more benefits than a single company operating selfishly in its own interest..... You can get co-operative advantage when what you are doing with your suppliers is better than what your competitors are doing.

Early supplier / purchaser relationships existing within large industries and large suppliers could be traced back to Taylorist⁶ structures. Rich and Hines⁷ observed that:

The traditional management doctrine, developed by such classical authors as Taylor during the era of mass consumption within relatively static markets, held that organisations should be vertically integrated from raw materials to the final product, using a bureaucratic and hierarchical management control system to ensure that profits are maximised through the manufacturing process. However, the long chains of command and the structuring of the enterprise into functions has proved to be inefficient when compared with more organic structures in the modern context ,

The attention to price as the predominant metric of supplier performance ignored the need to maintain high quality and delivery performance and any other benefits associated with supplier collaboration. As such, the supply process and material

distribution process were dislocated from the market. In the present post-mass production era the objective of members of successful supply chains is to derive the benefits of vertical integration and control without these dislocation problems. This process has already been engendered to some extent within industry. Rich and Hines identified that, "Farmer⁸ contends that this process of evolution is already underway in industry and that functional specialisation is slowly being replaced by a process-oriented management approach. New organisational configurations are concentrating on the management of core expertise and utilising supplier integration relationships to lower the associated risk of poor supplier performance".

However many problems still exist. Whilst there are examples of successful partnerships existing between purchasers and suppliers, such as that existing between Chrysler (USA) and many of its suppliers and also Ford (USA) and its suppliers , as described by Lawrence and Galati⁹ where the organisations had relationships based on four pillars, further expanded upon in Appendix 1, described as

- I Power Balancing*
- li Co-specialisation*
- lii Target Costing*
- IV Personal Ties*

There are many examples where the relationship is not so successful, however, and the relationship between supplier and purchaser can be judged to be unsatisfactory. This can have many basis, mistrust, lack of knowledge, poor specification or poor management but ultimately these issues cause problems right the way through the supply chain impacting on both the suppliers business and also the purchasers business, and profitable outcomes that may result from the transactions taking place. A mechanism should exist whereby the potential purchaser is able to evaluate suppliers by both tangible and

intangible aspects of the relationship.

It is possible to say that current texts, whilst defining the importance of intangible assets in the context of knowledge management¹⁰, best value decision evaluation¹¹, and also in defining value in terms of acquisitions¹² do little in defining measurement techniques that can be effectively utilised by purchasers in assessing these factors with regard to supply capability.

7.2. Phase 2: The Supply Chain –Value: Tangible and Intangible

As Goffin, Szejcowski et al¹³ observed

Both Kolay¹⁴ and Monczka¹⁵ stress that it is essential to audit the strategic capabilities of potential suppliers, such as their ability to contribute to product development. What are their technological capabilities? How will the supplier contribute towards the buyer's competitive advantage? These are the sort of questions that need to be asked when selecting suppliers. A complex model has been developed for use in regular audits of the relative value of suppliers - as an "asset base" - to the buyer (manufacturer). The drawback of this model is that the weighting factors for the decision criteria are highly contextual. In a review of five other prescriptive models for supplier selection, Ellram¹⁶ concluded that no model fits all situations adequately.

Co-operation between buyers and suppliers has moved from a transactional to a long-term basis. This new relationship is radically different - it is of strategic importance to the business. Consequently, cross-functional teamwork is essential in choosing suppliers^{17,18}. Most of the criteria for supplier choice are focused on quantifiable measures; however, other more qualitative factors need to be considered. For example, an assessment needs to be made of whether the culture of the supplier's organization can co-operate effectively with the buyer's organisational culture¹⁹.

Baily, Farmer, Jessop and Jones suggest that good suppliers have the following attributes:

1. Delivers on time

2. Provides consistent quality
3. Gives a good price
4. Has a stable background
5. Provides a good service backup
6. Is responsive to the customers' needs
7. Keeps promises
8. Provides technical support
9. Keeps the buyer informed on progress

If these are examined it can be seen that the second attribute is about the product itself and the others are about the service provided by the supplier at the time the product is made available, and generally throughout the life of the relationship with the customer. In the modern day parlance of value added there appear to be three areas of value being provided by the supplier. These are:

Value of the product itself Item 2

Value of the service provided when the product is made available
Items 1,3 and 4

Value of ongoing services provided that support the use of the product and the relationship between supplier and customer items 4,5,6,7, and 8

To simplify further there are two types of value being provided for the customer:

Intrinsic value

this is the value contained within the product and it is expressed in its specification. The provision of the value is in the conformance to that specification, and it is in such areas that quality is an important issue.

Extrinsic value

Firstly; this is the value contained in the service package that supports making the product available to the customer, and secondly; it is the value delivered in support of the use of the product over time, and the relationship between supplier and customer. The two areas here are also important quality issues because the first directly affects the effective and efficient operation of the customer during normal daily activities, and the second affects the medium to long term development of both customer and supplier. After all, they are in some measure dependent, one on the other.

It follows that an organisation in defining the intrinsic and extrinsic values it requires from the suppliers *will be able to specify the performance factors that support the delivery of these values, thus providing the standards to be measured.* The performance factors will differ from one situation to another even within a single company. The analysis of a particular situation will generate the relevant factors that make up satisfactory supplier performance. The nature of the value being added is also an important factor when considered from the ease of measurement point of view.

It can be said that where specifications are explicit and without ambiguity then the factors are *tangible*. Where specifications are not explicit and can be based on perceptions then the factors are *intangible*.

In summary then intangible and tangible value factors can be defined as follows:

Tangible factors

In terms of the intrinsic value of a product or service they are specifications that can be clearly defined and measured. The physical attributes of the product such as size, the materials it is made of, maximum allowed failure rate etc. It can also be in

terms of extrinsic value such as delivery performance to, either a specific schedule or within a specified lead-time. This will include measures such as service level, looking at delivery quantities.

Intangible factors

These factors can cover the whole aspect of the relationship between the customer and supplier. The degree to which the parties to the relationship can influence each other is an important element, as is the attitude of the two companies to each other. Such aspects can operate at the individual level as the employees of each company interact with each other in the performance of their jobs.

7.3. Phase 3: The Purchasing Function – Identifying Roles and Responsibilities

It is an inescapable fact that there are major differences between industrial sectors, and it follows that the roles and responsibilities of the purchasing function will differ, industrial sector to industrial sector. It is also possible that there will be differing roles and responsibilities within the purchasing function of a single company, however, it is extremely likely that for any company there will be one critical area coupled with one or more non-critical areas. A basic division by industry sector can cover the following:

- i. Extraction
- ii. Manufacturing
- iii. Retail and Distribution
- iv. Services

Within these sectors there will be a purchasing role that is key to the activities of the business. In fulfilling this role the purchasing department will operate certain processes and have particular information requirements that are specific for the given situation. The relationship with suppliers will be characterised by the processes and the information exchange-taking place across the boundary between the companies.

It would be useful to extend this division by describing the nature of the purchasing role being undertaken and dividing into the following categories:

- i. Production items
- ii. Consumables or Maintenance & Repair items. MRO
- iii. Capital Equipment

- iv. Goods for Resale
- v. Services

These two areas can be combined to give the following chart:

	Extractors of Raw Materials	Manufactures Of Goods	Distributors of Goods	Service Providers
Production Items		***		
Consumables or Maintenance, Repair & Operating Supplies (MRO)	***	*	*	***
Capital Equipment	***	***	***	***
Goods for Resale			***	
Services	*	*	*	*

*** Significant or "Mission Critical" areas

* Less important but still needs attention

7.4. Phase 4: The Focus Groups: Defining the Themes

In the manufacturing environment production items can be for different types of manufacturing process and it must be understood that the nature of the manufacturing process defines the purchasing process and thus the relationship with the supplier. The manufacturing process is a response to the requirements of the market place modified by the practical operational constraints that include those constraints coming from the external environment, from the constraints imposed by the operations of the supplying company. Once the specification of the product is defined there will be repeated delivery of the product, by the supplier, over an extended period of time.

Whilst buying production items is about optimising the core operations of the company within the context of the supply chain so as to satisfy customer demand, buying consumables, MRO items, is about managing availability of stock in the context of financial constraint. For many MRO items, controlling the level of stock, and hence the finance committed to that stock, is of paramount importance.

The purchase of capital equipment is another matter again. These are often purchases made on an infrequent basis with possibly a very substantial, detailed and complex specification. Once the equipment is in place and working, the customer is likely to require specialised support for repair and maintenance during the lifetime of the equipment. As with the manufacturing sector there are different types of products being purchased with widely varying characteristics defining the purchasing process.

The purchase of goods for resale is about selling on margin. A Company buys the product at one price and sells it on at a different price. Rarely are any operations performed on the product that change

its intrinsic value. In this case, it is the extrinsic value that is changing and being added to. Once the decision on which product to buy is made, availability and inventory control are the major issues. In addition, factors such as the promotion and advertising of the products in question, greatly influence the purchasing process.

The purchase of services is another specialised area where the specification of the intrinsic value can be difficult and complex. For example, in a cleaning contract careful consideration must be given to the definition of clean and how it is measured.

The purchasing process for any given situation is an inter-company dialogue that must take into account the operational activities of both companies and any other players in the supply chain. If the specification of the product is a supplier performance issue for the customer, then the customer cannot ignore the supplier's processes that manufacture and deliver the product. It is quite possible for the customer to put the supplier in the position of having to lower product specifications in order to meet the supplier's price demands. It is also possible for a contract to be so marginal in profit terms that the supplier gives the orders lower priority thus reducing delivery performance. The two sets of operations, the customer's and the supplier's, are inextricably linked. It can be argued that this is a relevant viewpoint for the mission critical products but not so for the subsidiary product areas. The degree to which the two sets of operations are linked may be seen as a function of the complexity of the transaction taking place and the level of information exchange at the boundary between the organisations. It follows therefore that the following factors must be taken into account when considering the setting of performance standards:

- i. The objectives of the transaction
- ii. The complexity of the transaction

- iii. Tangible benefits (value added)
- iv. Intangible benefits (value added)
- v. Process control (supplier's, customer's and purchasing processes)
- vi. Information exchange

These six themes were used as the basis for the focus group work discussed in the next section.

As detailed in the research methods industry focus groups were formed in order to develop an industry relevant questionnaire that would enable the research team to address the issues surrounding supplier performance benchmarking, areas to be addressed and methods by which they can be addressed.

Two groups were formed and the central themes of discussion were the six themes described.

The consensus of both focus groups emphasised the difficulties associated with the "soft" side issues. The hard side in terms of product specification, where a physical product was involved was relatively easy as was measuring the performance of the inter-organisational activities that ordered and delivered the product or service to site. The soft side dealt with areas such as:

1. Capability as opposed to theoretical capacity
 - a. Staff capability internal to the suppliers operations
 - b. Staff capability at the interface, supplier/customer
 - c. Resilience of processes internal to the supplier
 - d. Resilience of processes at supplier/customer interface

e. Improvement potential for a to d above

2. Planning capability of suppliers
3. Financial and operational stability
4. Willingness of supplier to commit to the relationship
5. Willingness and ability to undergo change
6. Technology assimilation

The groups were of the opinion that the soft issues must deal with the level of skills and knowledge available and their application. These skills and knowledge, residing within the companies forming the trading relationship, contribute to the performance of the relationship and thence to the performance of both companies. From a purchasing viewpoint the interest lies in the skills and knowledge, available and applied, that deliver both intrinsic and extrinsic value to the customer. The application of skills and knowledge was, in some measure, considered to be dependent on the information available. The important factor for information was, in the view of the groups, its integrity. Integrity of information was considered to be a function of its appropriateness, accuracy of content and destination, and timeliness.

The focus groups also considered the balance of power between suppliers and customers based on the levels of Skills, Knowledge and Information, coupled with the overall reliance each of the parties to the transaction must place on the other. An example of this was the purchase of a computer based application package for a business. The ideal situation is that the purchasing company knows

1. Exactly what it requires the software to do
2. Has a good understanding of the capability of computer systems
3. Is well versed in the management of change.

The supplying company:

1. Has a detailed knowledge of the industry it is supplying the package to
2. Has used this knowledge to develop a system that is appropriate for the prospective customer
3. Is well versed in managing change within a customer's environment

The reality is an imbalance with a bias towards the supplier. The purchaser needs to understand the nature of any imbalance that might exist for any transaction. This relates back to the objectives for the transaction and its complexity. The following grid can help focus on the issues.

Supplier/Customer Skills and Knowledge Grid

Skills and Knowledge of Supplier

		High	Low
Skills and Knowledge of customer	High		
	Low		

Relate to balance of power

The focus groups also considered the management of the supplier/customer relationship. Having decided on the performance factors, set the standards and put in place the measuring systems, consideration must be given to the relationship as it stands at the present and to consider what it may look like in the medium to long term. This was considered to very relevant given the need for continuous improvement in today's competitive world. In considering the management aspects, the group used the classic management roles of Planning, Organising and Control. These activities to be looked at in conjunction with the short to long term issues. Thus a second grid can be formed as a focussing aid.

Supplier/Customer Relationships

Setting and Measuring Supplier Performance

	Planning	Organising	Controlling
Strategic			
Tactical			
Operational			

Relating back to the skills and knowledge issue developed earlier, it was the focus groups conclusion that the application of skills and knowledge should be considered at all three levels shown in this grid. The implication is that the customer needs the supplier to perform at the strategic, tactical and operational levels in terms of planning, organisation and control. The customer needs to be able to set standards, measure performance against those standards and set in motion the actions necessary correct any variance. The measured performance will also become part of the information necessary if continuous improvement is to take place both within the suppliers' and customers operations.

Thus if the tangible values are set as:

1. Product/Service quality performance
2. Delivery performance
3. Price performance

Then these will be a function of the skills, knowledge and information performance of the supplying company.

7.5. Phase 5: Questionnaire and Outcomes

The Questionnaire is detailed in the Appendices

The questionnaire was developed to explore the issues in the context of different types of business in the following areas:

1. How important the skills, knowledge and information base of the mission critical suppliers is
2. Then how well suppliers performed in these three areas

These are explored at three levels in a business, viz. Operational, Tactical and Strategic. The exploration at three levels is necessary to explore the complexity of the relationships between customers and suppliers, and for any given industrial sector and purchasing type, the relevance of attempting to measure performance at these three levels. Complete satisfaction at the operational level is just a snapshot of 'now' and changes in circumstances can create a poorly performing supplier very quickly as it fails to adapt.

Further analysis is generated by exploring the interaction between customers and suppliers with questions to find out the degree of formality in any interactions. This is further extended by once again asking for a response based on the three levels, as shown above. This also explored the complexity of the relationships between customers and suppliers with the added bonus of exploring the relevance, dependent on industrial sector. In this section there is a question to find out the extent of Total Quality Management (TQM) programmes and whether these are implemented at all levels of the business. An additional question asks the respondents to consider the inter-

organisation processes other than those processes that handle the actual transaction.

The results of the questionnaire will enable the Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply to advise its members on supplier evaluation and performance issues, looking beyond delivery times and quantities, to building supplier, customer and overall supply chain performance.

7.6. Phase 6: Analysis of Questionnaire

The analysis of the questionnaire has been broken down into six main sections

- A) Basic company information
 - (1) Number of people employed
 - (2) Employed in purchasing department
 - (3) Industrial sector

- B) Purchasing Areas
 - (4) Mission critical purchasing area
 - (5) Subsidiary purchasing area
 - (6) Annual mission critical item spend

- C) Mission Critical Suppliers
 - (7) Expected delivery service standards
 - (8) Expected product / service standards
 - (9) Expected price performance targets

- D) Skills Base of Mission Critical Suppliers
 - (10) Skills base as a component of the business relationship
 - (11) Confidence in the skills base

- E) Knowledge Base of Mission Critical Suppliers
 - (12) Knowledge base as a of the business relationship
 - (13) Confidence in the knowledge base
 - (14) Confidence in information received
 - (15) Confidence in internal information

- F) Interaction with Mission Critical Supplier
 - (16) Interaction with suppliers
 - (17) TQM programmes
 - (18) Multidisciplinary teams
 - (19) Frequency of team meetings
 - (20) Confidence in supplier obligations
 - (21) Ease of business with supplier
 - (22) Utilisation of formal contract

7.6.1. Basic Company Information

In all 2500 Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply members were targeted in the survey. 270 returned questionnaires giving a response rate of just under 11%. This is comparable to the response rate of other questionnaires aimed at exploring benchmarking that were investigated in the initial literature review²⁰.

The following figure illustrate the answers to questions 1,2 and 3. These dealt with the basic areas of organisation size and purchasing department size, and also the industrial area occupied by the respondents.

Figure 2: Number of Employees

Figure 3: Numbers within the Purchasing Department

Figure 4: Industrial Sector

Figure 5: Mission Critical Purchasing Area

Mis_Crit_Purc_4 vs Frequency

Figure 6: Subsidiary Purchasing Areas

Sub_Purch_Area_5

Table 1: Average Annual Spend on Mission Critical Items

Spend on Mission Critical Items (£,000,000)	Frequency
No Value	27
[0.000 - 9.999]	61
[10.000 - 49.999]	98
[50.000 - 99.999]	29
[100.000 - 249.999]	23
[250.000 - 499.999]	13
[500.000 - 999.999]	5
[1000.000 - 2499.999]	9
[2500.000 - 4999.999]	5

If we compare questions 1 and 2, the number of people employed in total by the organisation with the number of purchasing professionals employed, detailed in the following table.

Table 2: Total Employed / Purchasing Employed

Q1. How Many People are Employed by Your Organisation

Employed_1 counts %columns %rows	Pur-Employ_2			Total
	0-5	6-15	16 Plus	
0-200	36	8	3	47
	34%	10%	4%	17%
	77%	17%	6%	
201-500	41	25	1	67
	39%	31%	1%	25%
	61%	37%	1%	
501 Plus	29	47	80	156
	27%	59%	95%	58%
	19%	30%	51%	
Total	106	80	84	270
	39%	30%	31%	

It becomes apparent that the largest data group came from individuals functioning within organisations of over 501 employees and purchasing departments of over 16 people, however with regard to the number of purchasing professionals employed within departments it can be seen that the department size was spread relatively equally over the groups with the most common being between 0-5 individuals at 39% of the total respondents. This cross tabulation is expanded to take into account the industrial sector, primary 'mission critical' purchasing area, subsidiary purchasing area and the average annual spend, detailed in the following table.

Table 3: Cross Tabulation of Basic Purchasing Information

Q1. How Many People are Employed by Your Organisation

Employed_1 counts %columns %rows	Ind_Sector_3					Total
	Not answered	Extraction	Manufacturing	Retail and Wholesale	Services Including Distribution	
0-200	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	32 16% 68%	5 42% 11%	10 18% 21%	47 17%
201-500	0 0% 0%	2 50% 3%	59 30% 88%	0 0% 0%	6 11% 9%	67 25%
501 Plus	1 100% 1%	2 50% 1%	105 54% 67%	7 58% 4%	41 72% 26%	156 58%
Total	1 0%	4 1%	196 73%	12 4%	57 21%	270

Q2. How Many People Work in the Purchasing Department

Pur-Employ_2 counts %columns %rows	Ind_Sector_3					Total
	Not answered	Extraction	Manufacturing	Retail and Wholesale	Services Including Distribution	
0-5	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	76 39% 72%	6 50% 6%	24 42% 23%	106 39%
6-15	1 100% 1%	3 75% 4%	59 30% 74%	2 17% 2%	15 26% 19%	80 30%
16 Plus	0 0% 0%	1 25% 1%	61 31% 73%	4 33% 5%	18 32% 21%	84 31%
Total	1 0%	4 1%	196 73%	12 4%	57 21%	270

The majority of the data points occur in the manufacturing sector, accounting for 196 of the respondents, with the secondary data group being the services accounting for 57 of the respondents, 21%. The next largest group was retail at only 4%. The main focus of the information must therefore be largely be interpreted as referring to these two industry groups, manufacturing and services. This does reflect the CIPS's membership group, the majority of which is made up of manufacturing organisations.

Of organisations over 501 employees manufacturing again formed the largest data group, with 54% of the manufacturing respondents employing over 501 people. This group represented 67% of the total organisations employing over 501 people. The skew in all industrial categories was towards the larger organisation this representing the largest percentage in all industrial categories.

The number of people employed in the purchasing departments did not show a similar skew. The largest data group was manufacturing again, but with a purchasing department size of between 0-5 people, this represented 39 % of the manufacturing group. Department sizes of 16 plus were less common within this sector with 61, 31% of the manufacturers reporting departments of this size.

Table 4: Industry Type Cross-Tabulated against Mission Critical Purchasing Area

Q4. Which of the Following Categories Describes the "Mission Critical" Purchasing Areas Best

Mis_Crit_Purc_4 counts %columns %rows	Ind_Sector_3					Total
	Not answered	Extraction	Manufacturing	Retail and Wholesale	Services Including Distribution	
Production Items	1 100% 0%	1 25% 0%	192 98% 94%	1 8% 0%	9 16% 4%	204 76%
Consumables or Maintance & Repair Items. MRO	0 0% 0%	2 50% 2%	52 27% 63%	2 17% 2%	27 47% 33%	83 31%
Capital Equipment	1 100% 1%	1 25% 1%	53 27% 68%	1 8% 1%	22 39% 28%	78 29%
Goods for Resale	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	32 16% 57%	10 83% 18%	14 25% 25%	56 21%
Services	1 100% 1%	4 100% 6%	27 14% 40%	2 17% 3%	33 58% 49%	67 25%
Total	1 0%	4 1%	196 73%	12 4%	57 21%	270

Table 5: Industry Type Cross Tabulated against Subsidiary Purchasing Areas

Q5. Which of the Following Categories Describes the Subsidiary Purchasing Areas Best

Sub_Purch_Area_5 counts %columns %rows	Ind_Sector_3					Total
	Not answered	Extraction	Manufacturing	Retail and Wholesale	Services Including Distribution	
Not answered	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	10 5% 77%	1 8% 8%	2 4% 15%	13 5%
Production Items	0 0% 0%	2 50% 5%	35 18% 80%	2 17% 5%	5 9% 11%	44 16%
Consumables or Maintance & Repair Items. MRO	1 100% 1%	2 50% 1%	133 68% 78%	7 58% 4%	28 49% 16%	171 63%
Capital Equipment	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	65 33% 71%	4 33% 4%	22 39% 24%	91 34%
Goods for Resale	1 100% 4%	0 0% 0%	23 12% 88%	1 8% 4%	1 2% 4%	26 10%
Services	0 0% 0%	1 25% 1%	73 37% 69%	4 33% 4%	28 49% 26%	106 39%
Total	1 0%	4 1%	196 73%	12 4%	57 21%	270

Table 6: Spend Cross tabulated against Industry Type and Mission Critical Purchasing Area

Q6. What is Your Average Annual Spend on "Mission Critical" Items?

Spend_6 counts %columns %rows	Ind_Sector_3					Mis_Crit_Purc_4					Total
	Not answered	Extraction	Manufacturing	Retail and Wholesale	Services Inculding Distribution	Production Items	Consumables or Mainatance & Repair Items. MRO	Capital Equipment	Goods for Resale	Services	
NV	0 0%	0 0%	23 12%	1 8%	3 5%	23 11%	6 7%	6 8%	6 11%	4 6%	27 10%
0.000..9.999	0 0%	0 0%	46 23%	2 17%	13 23%	46 23%	15 18%	11 14%	16 29%	11 16%	61 23%
10.000..49.999	0 0%	0 0%	74 75%	2 3%	20 21%	79 75%	34 25%	29 18%	21 26%	28 18%	98 36%
50.000..249.999	1 100%	1 25%	74 38%	2 17%	20 35%	79 39%	34 41%	29 37%	21 38%	28 42%	98 36%
50.000..249.999	0 0%	1 25%	34 17%	6 50%	11 19%	36 18%	13 16%	19 24%	11 20%	13 19%	52 19%
250.000..499.999	0 0%	1 25%	34 65%	6 12%	11 21%	36 69%	13 25%	19 37%	11 21%	13 25%	52 19%
250.000..499.999	0 0%	1 25%	9 5%	0 0%	3 5%	9 4%	6 7%	5 6%	0 0%	3 4%	13 5%
500.000..999.999	0 0%	0 0%	3 2%	1 8%	1 2%	3 1%	2 2%	1 1%	1 2%	1 1%	5 2%
500.000..999.999	0 0%	0 0%	3 60%	1 20%	1 20%	3 60%	2 40%	1 20%	1 20%	1 20%	5 20%
1000.000..4999.999	0 0%	1 25%	7 4%	0 0%	6 11%	8 4%	7 8%	7 9%	1 2%	7 10%	14 5%
1000.000..4999.999	0 0%	1 7%	7 50%	0 0%	6 43%	8 57%	7 50%	7 50%	1 7%	7 50%	14 5%
Total	1 0%	4 1%	196 73%	12 4%	57 21%	204 76%	83 31%	78 29%	56 21%	67 25%	270

The previous cross tabulations show that the majority of organisations that responded had mission critical spends less than 50 million pounds per year. Only 32 organisations had spends of over 250 million pounds per year. The largest category for both manufacturing and services was in the 10 to 50 million pound bracket. The majority of spending occurred in the area of production items with 204 respondents indicating that their organisations considered this a mission critical purchasing area, this is not surprising considering the strong manufacturing element of the survey population. 192, 94%, of the respondents that indicated that production items were a mission critical purchasing area were from the manufacturing sector. This data pattern did not significantly alter with the level of purchasing spend.

With regard to subsidiary areas, manufacturing again showed a large influence with consumables and maintenance and repair items forming the largest data point with 171 respondents, 131 of these from manufacturing indicating this as the subsidiary purchasing area.

In summary the main body of data to be used in evaluating suppliers and purchasers has been obtained from by and large a manufacturing base with services forming a secondary influence. The other industry groups can largely be disregarded from these results there not being a significant body of data on which to base judgements. Therefore the results of this evaluation can be considered relevant to these two industry groups with the primary relevance being to manufacturing industries. The suppliers to be evaluated, forming the largest part of this work are those supplying mission critical production items with consumables and maintenance and repair items as a secondary consideration.

Due to the low contribution to the data of the extraction and retail industries, 6.3% of the total response, these industry sectors have been excluded from the following analysis of supplier expectations which will concern itself with manufacturing and service industries.

7.6.2. Expectations of Suppliers: The Tangibles

The feedback to the questions regarding the purchasers expectations of the suppliers was measured through the use of a five point Likert scale.

Figure 7: Overall Our Suppliers Meet the Delivery Standards we Expect

Figure 8: Overall Our Suppliers meet the Product / Service Standards we Expect

Figure 9: Overall Our Suppliers Meet the Price Performance Targets we Expect

Table 7: Expected Delivery Performance Cross-Tabulated against Expected Price

Q7. Overall, Our Suppliers meet the delivery standards we expect

Meet_Deliv_Stan_7 counts %columns %rows	Meet_Price_Targ_9						Total
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
1	0	0	1	2	1	0	4
	0%	0%	5%	2%	1%	0%	2%
	0%	0%	25%	50%	25%	0%	
2	0	2	6	10	4	0	22
	0%	100%	27%	11%	3%	0%	9%
	0%	9%	27%	45%	18%	0%	
3	0	0	9	25	21	0	55
	0%	0%	41%	28%	17%	0%	22%
	0%	0%	16%	45%	38%	0%	
4	0	0	5	44	81	9	139
	0%	0%	23%	49%	67%	53%	55%
	0%	0%	4%	32%	58%	6%	
5	0	0	1	9	14	8	32
	0%	0%	5%	10%	12%	47%	13%
	0%	0%	3%	28%	44%	25%	
Total	1	2	22	90	121	17	253
	0%	1%	9%	36%	48%	7%	
Contingency coefficient	0.751						

Table 8: Expected Product / Service Quality Cross-Tabulated against Price

Q8. Overall our suppliers meet the product /service standards we expect, to what extent do you agree with this statement

Meet_Prod_Serv_8 counts %columns %rows	Meet_Price_Targ_9						Total
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	1 100% 100%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 0%
1	0 0% 0%	1 50% 100%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 0%
2	0 0% 0%	1 50% 14%	2 9% 29%	3 3% 43%	1 1% 14%	0 0% 0%	7 3%
3	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	6 27% 13%	27 30% 59%	13 11% 28%	0 0% 0%	46 18%
4	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	13 59% 8%	52 58% 33%	85 70% 53%	9 53% 6%	159 63%
5	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 5% 3%	8 9% 21%	22 18% 56%	8 47% 21%	39 15%
Total	1 0%	2 1%	22 9%	90 36%	121 48%	17 7%	253
Contingency coefficient	0.795						

Table 9: Expected Delivery Standards Cross-Tabulated against Product Quality

Q7. Overall, Our Suppliers meet the delivery standards we expect

Meet_Deliv_Stan_7 counts %columns %rows	Meet_Prod_Serv_8						Total
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
1	0	0	1	2	0	1	4
	0%	0%	14%	4%	0%	3%	2%
	0%	0%	25%	50%	0%	25%	
2	0	1	4	10	6	1	22
	0%	100%	57%	22%	4%	3%	9%
	0%	5%	18%	45%	27%	5%	
3	0	0	1	19	33	2	55
	0%	0%	14%	41%	21%	5%	22%
	0%	0%	2%	35%	60%	4%	
4	0	0	1	15	107	16	139
	0%	0%	14%	33%	67%	41%	55%
	0%	0%	1%	11%	77%	12%	
5	0	0	0	0	13	19	32
	0%	0%	0%	0%	8%	49%	13%
	0%	0%	0%	0%	41%	59%	
Total	1	1	7	46	159	39	253
	0%	0%	3%	18%	63%	15%	
Contingency coefficient						0.777	

As can be seen from the cross tabulations and the representations of the answers count for the three questions the physical, tangible, aspects of purchaser expectations are well correlated with correlation coefficients of over 70% in each case. Where physical factors such as quality are achieved to the purchasers satisfaction this is likely to hold true for price and delivery performance. In only a few cases did purchasers feel that they had excellent performance in one sphere without the other corresponding physical factors providing a similar level of satisfaction. Around half of the suppliers met the expected physical standards, judged as being cross-tabulated answers of 4 and over,

	-Tabulated (4 and Above)
Quality – Price	44%
Price – Price	49%
Quality – Service	61.3

This illustrates that by and large purchasers have a degree of confidence in judging suppliers on these physical, tangible, aspects, as 4% or less of the cross-tabulated data fell in the 1 to 2 scale – poor performance. However when benchmarking and evaluating suppliers²¹,

What should a benchmarking team look for, say, in evaluating manufacturing excellence? Most focus on physical factorsthese are the easiest to measure. But many veterans of the process say that the edge enjoyed by competitive firms often lies elsewhere. That means searching out hard-to-quantify, and even harder to mimic, qualities like management techniques, joint ventures and relationships with suppliers and customers- a time-consuming process. Unsurprisingly, some firms

give up the ghost before they find what they are looking for.

7.6.3. Expectations of Suppliers: The Intangibles

The next section explores the perception of the skills base, the importance of the skills base, the confidence in the skills base of the supplier. The perceived importance and confidence in the knowledge base of the supplier is also addressed.

Figure 10: Importance of the Skills Base of Suppliers: Operational, Tactical and Strategic Level

Figure 11: Confidence in the Skills Base of Suppliers: Operational, Tactical and Strategic Level

Table 10: Cross-Tabulation Importance / Confidence: Skills base of Suppliers at all Levels

Q10i. Operational Level

Skill_Imp_Com_OP_10 counts %columns %rows	Skill_Conf_OP_11						Skill_Conf_TC_11						Skill_Conf_ST_11					Total		
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4		5	
2	0 0% 0%	1 50% 14%	3 23% 43%	1 1% 14%	2 2% 29%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	2 11% 29%	5 4% 71%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 43%	3 9% 29%	2 2% 29%	2 2% 29%	0 0% 0%	7 3%
3	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 8% 4%	18 24% 64%	8 6% 29%	1 3% 4%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	2 11% 7%	21 19% 75%	4 4% 14%	1 4% 4%	0 0% 0%	1 17% 4%	5 14% 18%	13 13% 46%	9 10% 32%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	28 11%
4	1 50% 1%	0 0% 0%	7 54% 7%	33 44% 31%	59 46% 55%	7 22% 7%	2 33% 2%	1 100% 1%	9 47% 8%	48 42% 45%	42 46% 39%	5 22% 5%	1 20% 1%	4 67% 4%	13 37% 12%	42 43% 39%	37 42% 35%	10 45% 9%	107 42%	
5	1 50% 1%	1 50% 1%	2 15% 2%	23 31% 21%	60 47% 54%	24 75% 22%	4 67% 4%	0 0% 0%	6 32% 5%	39 35% 35%	45 49% 41%	17 74% 15%	4 80% 4%	1 17% 1%	14 40% 13%	40 41% 36%	40 45% 36%	12 55% 11%	111 44%	
Total	2 1%	2 1%	13 5%	75 30%	129 51%	32 13%	6 2%	1 0%	19 8%	113 45%	91 36%	23 9%	5 2%	6 2%	35 14%	97 38%	88 35%	22 9%	253	
Contingency coefficient	0.470						0.339						0.233							

Table 11: Cross-Tabulation: Tactical Importance / Confidence: Skills base of Suppliers at all Levels

Q10ii. Tactical Level

Skill_Imp_Com_TC_10 counts %columns %rows	Skill_Conf_OP_11						Skill_Conf_TC_11						Skill_Conf_ST_11						Total	
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5		
Not answered	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 1%	0 0%	1 17%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 1%	0 0%	1 0%	
2	0 0%	0 0%	3 23%	2 3%	6 5%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	5 26%	2 2%	4 4%	0 0%	0 0%	2 33%	4 11%	4 4%	1 1%	0 0%	11 4%	
3	0 0%	0 0%	2 15%	28 37%	26 20%	5 16%	1 17%	0 0%	4 21%	42 37%	12 13%	2 9%	1 20%	1 17%	9 26%	27 28%	21 24%	2 9%	61 24%	
4	0 0%	2 100%	4 31%	26 35%	63 49%	14 44%	2 33%	1 100%	8 42%	46 41%	43 47%	9 39%	2 40%	3 50%	13 37%	42 43%	38 43%	11 50%	109 43%	
5	0 0%	2 100%	0 0%	4 31%	19 25%	33 26%	13 41%	2 33%	0 0%	2 11%	23 20%	32 35%	12 52%	2 40%	0 0%	9 26%	24 25%	27 31%	9 41%	71 28%
Total	2 1%	2 1%	13 5%	75 30%	129 51%	32 13%	6 2%	1 0%	19 8%	113 45%	91 36%	23 9%	5 2%	6 2%	35 14%	97 38%	88 35%	22 9%	253	
Contingency coefficient	0.343						0.519						0.316							

Table 12: Cross-Tabulation Strategic Importance / Confidence: Skills base of Suppliers at all Levels

Q10iii. Strategic Level

Skill_Imp_Com_ST_10 counts %columns %rows	Skill_Conf_OP_11						Skill_Conf_TC_11						Skill_Conf_ST_11						Total	
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5		
1	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	3 2% 60%	2 6% 40%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	3 3% 60%	1 1% 20%	1 4% 20%	0 0% 0%	3 50% 60%	1 3% 20%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 20%	0 0% 0%	1 5% 20%	5 2%
2	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	2 15% 13%	6 8% 40%	7 5% 47%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	4 21% 27%	10 9% 67%	1 1% 7%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 53%	8 23% 27%	4 4% 27%	3 3% 20%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	15 6%
3	1 50% 2%	2 100% 4%	2 15% 4%	19 25% 35%	24 19% 44%	7 22% 13%	2 33% 4%	0 0% 0%	4 21% 7%	27 24% 49%	19 21% 35%	3 13% 5%	2 40% 4%	0 0% 0%	5 14% 9%	36 37% 65%	11 12% 20%	1 5% 2%	1 5% 2%	55 22%
4	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	4 31% 4%	26 35% 28%	55 43% 59%	9 28% 10%	3 50% 3%	1 100% 1%	8 42% 9%	39 35% 41%	36 40% 38%	7 30% 7%	2 40% 2%	3 50% 3%	11 31% 12%	30 31% 32%	44 50% 47%	4 18% 4%	4 18% 4%	94 37%
5	1 50% 1%	0 0% 0%	5 38% 6%	24 32% 29%	40 31% 48%	14 44% 17%	1 17% 1%	0 0% 0%	3 16% 4%	34 30% 40%	34 37% 40%	12 52% 14%	1 20% 1%	0 0% 0%	10 29% 12%	27 28% 32%	30 34% 36%	16 73% 19%	16 73% 19%	84 33%
Total	2 1%	2 1%	13 5%	75 30%	129 51%	32 13%	6 2%	1 0%	19 8%	113 45%	91 36%	23 9%	5 2%	6 2%	35 14%	97 38%	88 35%	22 9%	22 9%	253
Contingency coefficient	0.288						0.304						0.592							

The graphs illustrating the responses to questions 10 and 11 dealing with the purchasers consideration of the importance of the suppliers skills base and the purchasers confidence in that skills base show that as the level of the importance of the skills base rises, i.e. from operational to strategic the level of recognised contribution to the business relationship decreases. In the following table the answers to questions 10 and 11 have been adjusted to group together the response to show the relative skew of the data as the level of strategic impact changes.

Table 13: Skew of Response to the Importance of the Suppliers Skills Base

1 – Not Important 5 – Very Important	(Not answered)	1 and 2	3	4 and 5
Operational	0.0%	2.8%	11.1%	86.2%
Tactical	0.4%	4.3%	24.1%	71.1%
Strategic	0.0%	7.9%	21.7%	70.4%

Table 14: Skew of Response to the Confidence in the Suppliers Skills Base

1 – Not Important 5 – Very Important	(Not answered)	1 and 2	3	4 and 5
Operational	0.8%	5.9%	29.6%	63.6%
Tactical	2.4%	7.9%	44.7%	45.1%
Strategic	2.0%	16.2%	38.3%	43.5%

Also the correlation's detailed in the cross-tabulations between the acknowledgement of, and the confidence in, the suppliers skills base are highest where the level of transaction complexity coincides.

Taking this analysis a stage further we can examine the

purchasers consideration of the suppliers knowledge base as an important component of the business relationship and also the purchasers confidence in the knowledge base of the supplier.

Figure 12: The Perception of the Supplier Knowledge Base as an Important Component of the Business Relationship at the Operational, Tactical and Strategic Level

Figure 13: Purchaser Confidence in the Knowledge Base of the Supplier at the Operational, Tactical and Strategic Levels

Table 15: Cross-Tabulation Operational Importance / Confidence: Knowledge Base of Suppliers at all Levels

Q12i. Operational Level

Know_Supp_OP_12 counts %columns %rows	Know_Conf_OP_13						Know_Conf_TC_13						Know_Conf_ST_13						Total	
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5		
Not answered	1 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 100%
2	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	5 6%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 5%	4 4%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 3%	4 4%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	5 2%
3	0 0%	2 67%	3 21%	27 32%	10 8%	1 3%	0 0%	2 50%	5 24%	25 24%	11 11%	0 0%	0 0%	2 40%	10 30%	18 18%	13 14%	0 0%	43 17%	
4	0 0%	1 33%	8 57%	33 39%	64 54%	3 9%	1 50%	1 25%	8 38%	46 44%	49 48%	4 21%	0 0%	2 40%	12 36%	43 42%	46 50%	6 30%	109 43%	
5	0 0%	0 0%	3 21%	19 23%	44 37%	29 88%	0 0%	1 25%	7 33%	29 28%	43 42%	15 79%	0 0%	1 20%	10 30%	37 36%	33 36%	14 70%	95 38%	
Total	1 0%	3 1%	14 6%	84 33%	118 47%	33 13%	2 1%	4 2%	21 8%	104 41%	103 41%	19 8%	1 0%	5 2%	33 13%	102 40%	92 36%	20 8%	253	
Contingency coefficient	0.753						0.621						0.722							

Table 16: Cross-Tabulation Tactical Importance / Confidence: Knowledge Base of Suppliers at all Levels

Q12ii. Tactical Level

Know_Supp_TC_12 counts %columns %rows	Know_Conf_OP_13						Know_Conf_TC_13						Know_Conf_ST_13						Total
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	1 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 1%	0 0%	2 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 1%	0 0%	2 1%
1	50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	50% 0%	0 0%	100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	50% 0%	0 0%	0 0%
2	0 0%	1 33%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 25%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
3	0 0%	0 0%	1 7%	5 6%	2 2%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	3 14%	5 5%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 20%	2 6%	5 5%	0 0%	0 0%	8 3%
4	0 0%	0 0%	1 12%	5 62%	2 25%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	3 38%	5 62%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 12%	2 25%	5 62%	0 0%	0 0%	59 23%
5	0 0%	1 33%	5 36%	28 33%	22 19%	3 9%	0 0%	2 50%	7 33%	39 38%	10 10%	1 5%	0 0%	2 40%	13 39%	29 28%	14 15%	1 5%	59 23%
6	0 0%	2 2%	8 8%	47% 47%	37% 37%	5 5%	0 0%	3 3%	12% 12%	66% 66%	17% 17%	2 2%	0 0%	3 3%	22% 22%	49% 49%	24% 24%	2 2%	111 44%
7	0 0%	1 33%	5 36%	37 44%	58 49%	10 30%	0 0%	1 25%	7 33%	41 39%	59 57%	3 16%	0 0%	1 20%	12 36%	44 43%	48 43%	6 5%	111 44%
8	0 0%	0 0%	3 21%	14 17%	35 30%	20 61%	0 0%	0 0%	4 19%	19 18%	34 33%	15 79%	0 0%	0 0%	6 18%	24 24%	29 32%	13 65%	72 28%
9	0 0%	0 0%	4 4%	19% 19%	49% 49%	28% 28%	0 0%	0 0%	6% 6%	26% 26%	47% 47%	21% 21%	0 0%	0 0%	8% 8%	33% 33%	40% 40%	18% 18%	72 28%
Total	1 0%	3 1%	14 6%	84 33%	118 47%	33 13%	2 1%	4 2%	21 8%	104 41%	103 41%	19 8%	1 0%	5 2%	33 13%	102 40%	92 36%	20 8%	253
Contingency coefficient	0.700						0.776						0.677						

Table 17: Cross-Tabulation: Strategic Importance / Confidence: Knowledge Base of Suppliers at all Levels

Q12iii. Strategic Level

Know_Supp_ST_12 counts %columns %rows	Know_Conf_OP_13						Know_Conf_TC_13						Know_Conf_ST_13						Total	
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5		
Not answered	1 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	1 0%
1	0 0%	1 33%	0 0%	0 0%	1 1%	0 0%	0 0%	1 25%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	2 40%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	2 1%
2	0 0%	0 0%	1 7%	5 6%	3 3%	1 3%	0 0%	0 0%	2 10%	6 6%	2 2%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	7 21%	3 3%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	10 4%
3	0 0%	1 33%	5 36%	27 32%	24 20%	4 12%	0 0%	2 50%	8 38%	37 36%	12 12%	2 11%	0 0%	2 40%	8 24%	41 40%	9 10%	1 5%	61 24%	
4	0 0%	0 0%	2 14%	32 38%	50 42%	10 30%	1 50%	0 0%	6 29%	32 31%	52 50%	3 16%	0 0%	0 0%	11 33%	35 34%	46 50%	2 10%	94 37%	
5	0 0%	1 33%	6 43%	20 24%	40 34%	18 55%	0 0%	1 25%	4 19%	29 28%	37 36%	14 74%	0 0%	1 20%	7 21%	23 23%	37 40%	17 85%	85 34%	
Total	1 0%	3 1%	14 6%	84 33%	118 47%	33 13%	2 1%	4 2%	21 8%	104 41%	103 41%	19 8%	1 0%	5 2%	33 13%	102 40%	92 36%	20 8%	253	
Contingency coefficient	0.744						0.669						0.796							

Table 18: Skew of Response to the Confidence in the Suppliers Skills Base

	(Not answered)	1 and 2	3	4 and 5
Operational	0.4%	2.6%	15.9%	81.1%
Tactical	0.7%	3.7%	23.0%	72.6%
Strategic	0.4%	5.6%	22.6%	71.5%

Table 19: Skew of Response to the Confidence in the Suppliers Skills Base

	(Not answered)	1 and 2	3	4 and 5
Operational	0.4%	7.0%	33.7%	58.9%
Tactical	0.7%	11.5%	40.4%	47.4%
Strategic	0.4%	15.9%	40.0%	43.7%

As can be seen from the cross tabulations and representations of the data, including the data skew apparent in the previous tables we can determine that, as with the skills base, the knowledge base of the suppliers is considered to be at its most important, and also subject to the most confidence at the operational level, and less so at the strategic level where the relationship is more complex. Again at all levels, operational, tactical and strategic the consideration of importance and confidence in the knowledge base are congruent as shown by the coefficients in the cross tabulations.

If the two sets of data, skills and knowledge are combined it becomes apparent that purchasers see the relationship between the two factors, where supplier skills are considered to be high then supplier knowledge is also perceived to be high, again shown by the coefficient of the two groups of data. The extensive cross-tabulation of the perception of skills and knowledge held by the purchasers in their suppliers is detailed in full in the appendices.

7.6.4. Expectation of Suppliers: Information

Confidence in information received from suppliers, and also the way in which that information is processed by the purchaser is of vital importance in the supply chain. Mangaliso²² noted, when discussing the work of Procter²³, In relation to his own studies on the usefulness of management information that

Managers are often faced with situations where "there is plenty of information around - but too much of the wrong kind and not enough of the right kind." Proctor (1991) further noted that the kinds of complaints usually encountered regarding information are: that information is too dispersed to be useful (lack of aggregation), it arrives too late to be useful (lack of timeliness), and it arrives in a form that leaves no idea of its accuracy and therefore lacks focus (lack of scope).

Lack of confidence, and trust, in the supplier and the information generated by them and within the purchasers own department can cause delays in the supply chain and erode profit and also confidence, causing stockpiling in the face of uncertain information. Christian Cull²⁴ when talking to Graham Booth, Supply Chain Development Director of Tesco PLC, about Tesco's relationship with its suppliers noted that,

Improvements in the supply chain do not happen overnight... with suspicion the order of the day. Suspicion breeds to lack of confidence and causes expensive delay. It costs money every time a product stops moving adding extra expense to the supply chain. As Booth says: "Everyone builds in

safety factors throughout the supply chain....."

Each safety point brings a skew.

Questions 14 to 15 in the questionnaire dealt with the confidence in the information received from suppliers, and also the purchasing professionals information generated within their own company.

Figure 14: Confidence in Information Received from Suppliers

Figure 15: Confidence in Internal Information

**Table 20: Cross-Tabulation of Confidence in Supplier and Purchaser
Internal Information**

Q14. Overall, my company has confidence in the information received from its suppliers.

Inf_Conf_14 counts %columns %rows	Purc_Conf_Inf_15					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 1% 100%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 0%
1	1 9% 100%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 0%
2	2 18% 10%	8 19% 38%	7 7% 33%	4 5% 19%	0 0% 0%	21 8%
3	3 27% 4%	12 29% 15%	38 37% 48%	26 31% 33%	0 0% 0%	79 31%
4	3 27% 2%	19 45% 15%	50 49% 38%	49 58% 37%	10 77% 8%	131 52%
5	2 18% 10%	3 7% 15%	6 6% 30%	6 7% 30%	3 23% 15%	20 8%
Total	11 4%	42 17%	102 40%	85 34%	13 5%	253
Contingency coefficient	0.401					

Figure 16: Confidence in Internal and Supplier Generated Information

Interestingly the cross-tabulation and the graph show that purchasers in general have more confidence in the information generated by their suppliers than that generated and received from within their own organisation. This again confirms the results generated by the exploration of the tangible aspects of the relationship. Purchasers in general do have confidence in the tangible, physical aspects of the supplier, even more so than in the internal aspects of their own organisations information. This is in line with current benchmarking and evaluating practices largely based on physical measurable points. The organisation buying manufactured components from a specialist supplier will have investigated quality, delivery performance and price and will by and large trust the reports of this information generated by the supplier. This is of course largely at the operational level, as shown by the skills and knowledge questions and also the questions relating to delivery, quality and price.

7.6.5. Expectation of Supplier: Working with the Supplier

Interacting with the supplier is a vital part of the business relationship, highly dependant of course on the level of complexity of the business relationship and the nature of the goods or services supplied.

As the following Figure shows the level of this interaction drops as the relationship becomes more complex, from operational to strategic. This determines that as the immediacy of the interaction diminishes from the day to day level required for production or provision of services then the level to which the purchaser assumes responsibility for the transaction increases, keeping the actions within the organisation.

Figure 17: Extent of Interaction with Mission Critical Suppliers

As organisations operate programmes such as TQM, however, the degree of interaction increases at the operational, tactical and strategic levels, as shown in the following table. With a greater frequency of purchasing practitioners reporting a high level of supplier interaction where a TQM programme was in place.

Table 21: Interaction in the 46.3 % of Organisations Not Operating a TQM Programme

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational	2.4%	6.3%	17.8%	43.1%	30.4%
Tactical	1.6%	12.4%	33.5%	37.5%	15.1%
Strategic	9.1%	16.3%	30.6%	27.8%	16.3%

Table 22: Supplier Interaction in the 53.8 % of Organisations Operating a TQM Programme

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational	3.0%	4.4%	14.1%	41.5%	37.0%
Tactical	0.0%	9.0%	30.6%	40.3%	20.1%
Strategic	5.9%	9.6%	31.9%	34.8%	17.8%

Table 23: Perception of Ease of Business With Suppliers Dependant on the Existence of a TQM Programme

Q17. Does your company have a total quality management programme that the "mission critical" suppliers in co-ordinated "continuous programmes"

TQM_17 counts %columns %rows	Easy_Bus_MissCrt_21						Total
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	0 0% 0%	1 1% 50%	1 1% 50%	0 0% 0%	2 1%
Yes	2 40% 1%	2 33% 1%	11 46% 8%	49 52% 36%	61 56% 45%	10 62% 7%	135 53%
No	3 60% 3%	4 67% 3%	13 54% 11%	44 47% 38%	46 43% 40%	6 38% 5%	116 46%
Total	5 2%	6 2%	24 9%	94 37%	108 43%	16 6%	253

The response to the questionnaire shows that this reasoning, applied to TQM programmes operated with the suppliers increasing the ease of business also translates through to the operation of joint multidisciplinary teams with suppliers, whereby if the purchaser operates a TQM programme they are twice as likely to operate multidisciplinary teams with mission critical suppliers at all levels, operational, tactical or strategic. Again the operation of such teams increase the perceived ease of business with the supplier. The following restricted cross tabulations show that where a TQM programme is in place, and multidisciplinary teams are in operation the purchaser finds the business relationship with the supplier much easier. The frequency of these meeting as one might expects decreases with the immediacy and complexity of the supply relationship. At the strategic level the meetings occur less frequently than at the operational level.

Figure 18: Frequency of Joint Meetings with Suppliers for Organisations Operating Multidisciplinary Teams

Table 24: Perceived Ease of Business with Suppliers Compared to the Existence of Multidisciplinary Teams and TQM Programmes

Q21. How easy is it to do business with the company's "Mission critical" suppliers?

Easy_Bus_MissCrt_21 counts	Mul_Dip_Team_OP_18		Mul_Dip_Team_TC_18			Mul_Dip_Team_ST_18			Total
	Yes	No	Not answered	Yes	No	Not answered	Yes	No	
Not answered	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	2
1	1	1	0	2	0	0	1	1	2
2	8	3	0	5	6	0	4	7	11
3	37	12	0	36	13	0	28	21	49
4	49	12	1	40	20	2	37	22	61
5	10	0	1	3	6	1	6	3	10
Total	106	29	2	86	47	3	76	56	135

Table 25: Perceived Ease of Business with Suppliers Compared to the Existence of Multidisciplinary Teams But No TQM Programmes

Q21. How easy is it to do business with the company's "Mission critical" suppliers?

Easy_Bus_MissCrt_21 counts	Mul_Dip_Team_OP_18		Mul_Dip_Team_TC_18		Mul_Dip_Team_ST_18		Total
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Not answered	1	2	0	3	0	3	3
1	0	4	0	4	0	4	4
2	7	6	5	8	3	10	13
3	24	20	11	33	10	34	44
4	15	31	14	32	12	34	46
5	3	3	1	5	2	4	6
Total	50	66	31	85	27	89	116

The clear impact of TQM programmes and multidisciplinary teams on perceived ease of business is interesting in that it emphasises that TQM programmes do not just impact on the physical, and often emphasised, tangible benefits of quality management.

The confidence that the supplier will meet the obligations resulting from these meetings can be compared to the level to which the purchasers organisation interacts with the supplier. The higher levels of interaction show that the purchaser has more confidence that the supplier will meet their obligations that have resulted from the joint meetings.

Finally the questionnaire reported on the use of the formal contract as a means of measuring the performance of the supplier. The results showed that as a means of measurement the formal contract is not widely regarded by purchasing practitioners, with only 30% agreeing that the formal contract was used as the basis for measuring performance.

Table 26: The Use of the Formal Contract for Measuring Performance

Strongly Disagree 1- 5- Strongly Agree	Frequency	Percentage
1	32	12.7
2	65	25.9
3	76	30.3
4	54	21.5
5	24	9.6

With respect to the purchasers use of the formal contract and the ease of business it can be seen that, there is little correlation between the data points, i.e. where the purchaser considers business with the mission critical supplier is easy (4 on the Likert scale) this is not reflected in the use of the formal contract which varies by less than three percent around the median value over the whole Likert scale.

Table 27: Ease of Business and the Use of the Formal Contract as a Means of Measuring Performance

Q21. How easy is it to do business with the company's "Mission critical" suppliers?

Easy_Bus_MissCrt_21 counts %columns	Form_Contr_Meas_22						Total
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	
Not answered	1 50%	0 0%	4 6%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	5 2%
1	0 0%	1 3%	2 3%	0 0%	2 4%	1 4%	6 2%
2	1 50%	6 19%	6 9%	3 4%	5 9%	3 12%	24 9%
3	0 0%	7 22%	22 34%	39 51%	20 37%	6 25%	94 37%
4	0 0%	15 47%	28 43%	31 41%	23 43%	11 46%	108 43%
5	0 0%	3 9%	3 5%	3 4%	4 7%	3 12%	16 6%
Total	2	32	65	76	54	24	253

7.7. Hypotheses

As was stated earlier this piece of work has four central hypotheses which will be examined in detail, relevant to the findings of the survey.

- H-1. Physical aspects of the supply chain such as delivery performance, price and quality whilst being vital to good manufacturing and service provision are given factors and are not responsible for the perceived ease of business with the supplier, and the success of the supply relationship.
- H-2. The formal contract, and tangible procedures such as TQM, as a form of physical measurement have little impact on the ease of business and the success of the supply relationship.
- H-3. Purchaser confidence in, and acknowledgement of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier, the interaction between the parties and the confidence in the information received is directly related to the perceived ease of the supply relationship.
- H-4. The frequency of interaction between the purchaser and supplier does not directly impinge on the ease of business, but rather it is the quality of interaction increases the ease of business and the potential success of the supply relationship

7.7.1. H-1: The Relevance of Physical Aspects of Supply to the Success of the Supply Relationship and the Ease of Business

The physical aspects of supply have always been important to the supply process, Goffin et al²⁵ commented that, when investigating how companies should select suppliers for the purpose of supply base reduction that...

Although this is the critical question facing management²⁶, "there appears to be little documentation on the method used for supplier selection"²⁷. However, the decision criteria used in traditional approaches to purchasing were unit price (first), followed by quality and speed of delivery. Price has often been the factor given the main emphasis: "the choice of lowest price, is perhaps one of the most defined characteristics of primitive purchasing". Quality tended to be looked at from the conformance point of view, i.e. if the supplier's quality simply met the current required level, then this was acceptable. A better way to select suppliers is by looking not only at current quality but also at their quality record, their potential for further improvement^{28, 29}, and their use of total quality management (TQM)^{30, 31}

Current thinking proposes a wide set of factors to be considered during supplier selection. It is important to look not only at today's unit price but also the total purchase costs (including ordering, transport and inventory costs³²) and the potential for price reduction^{33, 34, 35}.

These again are physical measures based around the implementation of procedures and processes, however these procedures are a reflection of tangible measurables. In this study where the tangible and intangible elements of the relationship have been separated it becomes apparent that conformance to procedure and specification has little impact on the perceived ease of business with the supplier, see appendices. This does not mean to say that if these physical factors were uncontrolled that the ease of business relations would be unaffected, but that this element of the business relationship is well within the control of the purchasing professionals who responded to the questionnaire, and can almost be taken as a prerequisite, and in the main it is the other intangible factors that are responsible for the perceived success of the supply relationship. A definition of TQM by Merlyn and Parkinson³⁶ suggests that TQM is, " The integration of quality management methods, concepts, and beliefs into the culture of the organization to bring about continuous improvement". This definition would sit well with the work carried by Parzinger et al³⁷ which followed on from Powell's³⁸ 1995 work on judging the success of TQM within organisations where it was determined that

One of the objectives of Powell's study (1995) was to examine TQM as a potential source of sustainable competitive advantage. The findings suggest that most features generally associated with TQM - such as quality training, process improvement and benchmarking - do not generally produce advantage.

This would suggest that other intangible features of TQM and operating multidisciplinary teams with suppliers is responsible for the increased ease of business with the supplier. TQM in itself is a metaphor, not a set of procedures that can be

implemented for step by step business success. Glaser³⁹ commented that,

Our behaviour as human beings is governed by complex sets of rules. Within organizations these rules are codified by procedures manuals. And within the normal flow of human interaction language plays a major part in communicating these rules, giving us permission to undertake some behaviours and avoid doing others. Unfortunately a lot of management thinking is coloured by what philosophers call the doctrine of misplaced concreteness. What this means, very simply, is that sometimes we make the mistake of thinking that because something can be named or described it actually has an existence. Or because there is a new way of describing something we may think that the new description reflects a new phenomenon.

The implementation of TQM as a physical set of procedures is unlikely to produce advantage in the purchaser supplier relationship, however the opening up of communication between the supplier and the purchaser enabled through the initiation of multidisciplinary teams engendered by TQM is likely to increase the probability of a successful supply relationship.

The response to the questionnaire shows that there was not a significant pattern of response among the purchasing practitioners who, while considering the tangible factors to be under control in the majority, did not perceive this as having a visible effect on the ease of business with the mission critical suppliers. The inter-company teamwork element of TQM increases interaction and also integration of the suppliers operations into the purchasers, Rich and Hines⁴⁰ contend that,

The integration of the supply base represents a source of competitive advantage. This is achieved when suppliers are focused on their customers' market requirements and can effectively change their behaviour as a result. At this stage, new relationships and means of influencing the strategies and operating practices employed within the supply chain need to be established and managed collaboratively. In contrast with the classical approach, this attempt to control and align the activities of suppliers is achieved through influence rather than the exercise of adversarial power.

They also draw attention to the work of Stevens⁴¹ which suggests that companies are evolving through 'backward integration' whereby they integrate themselves further and further back through the supply chain in order to achieve competitive advantage through suppliers. He also suggests four stages in this process, detailed in Rich and Hines work, which have been summarised below, and are listed in full in the appendices.

- (i) *The baseline organization*, this organization operates the classical system of management, with the motivation of profit maximisation and a high level of functional specialisation
- (ii) *The functionally integrated company*, this organization has begun to erode the hierarchical structure and short-term financial focus by concentrating on customer service criteria and sales order processing.
- (iii) *The internally integrated company*, this organization has continued to restructure and align the activities of manufacturing and purchasing to create a systems

approach to customer service..... The planning horizon has also extended from the short term to the medium term and involves a limited interaction with suppliers

(iv) *The externally integrated company*, this organisational state involves the externalisation of the alignment process and the integration of the supply base with the demands of the consumer in a transparent system of materials and information exchange..... and has recognised the importance of external supply-chain management strategies and the need to synchronise the supply process. The company operates internal cross-functional management structures, which may be product related, and typically develop supplier networking groups.

If this is the case then the questionnaire would show that the organisations approached, which have achieved a professional supply capability due to the fact that they have senior level members within the CIPS and in the majority turnovers in excess of £10 million pounds, would be internally integrated and in most cases achieved a degree of external integration. This can be seen where the data shows that the higher the level of interaction, the greater the perceived ease of business. Note that this is not dependant not the physical factors of price, delivery and quality which do not show an influence over the perceived ease of business, as proved earlier in this report, *it becomes apparent that conformance to procedure and specification has little impact on the perceived ease of business with the suppliers. This does not mean to say that if these physical factors were uncontrolled that the ease of business relations would be unaffected, but that this element of the business relationship is well within the control of the purchasing professionals*

In summary this supports hypothesis H1, that ***Physical aspects of the supply chain such as delivery performance, price and quality whilst being vital to good manufacturing and service provision are given factors and are not responsible for the perceived ease of business with the supplier, and the success of the supply relationship.***

7.7.2. H-2: The Impact of the Formal Contract and Tangible Procedures such as TQM, as a Form of Physical Measurement, on the Supply Relationship

As has been shown TQM introduced within an organisation does not, as a physical set of procedures, automatically produce better supply relationships. Rich and Hines, touch on the impact of the formal contract as a form of supply measurement when discussing long term supplier associations, they propose that,

....deliberate strategy to align and integrate the external productive resources, and the strategies of suppliers through the development of collaborative relationships, explicitly recognizes the dependency between the organization and its sub-contracting network. ***The strategy also represents a means of creating an informal contract to supply, whereby the formal contract between organizations is supplemented with an attention to standardizing procedures and the manner in which business is conducted. This may be termed the socialization process.*** The strategy also attempts to localize the pressures of the consumer market in the measurement and expectations of the supply base. The strategy recognizes the limitations of a price-oriented approach and attempts to create a system which is focused on the timely exchange of materials and information.

This again stresses the importance of interaction between the purchaser and the supplier as way of increasing ease of business and purchaser / supplier integration. As was demonstrated in the questionnaire the findings determined that

the existence of a TQM programmes intangible elements increased the perceived ease of business and confidence in the suppliers ability to meet obligations. The basis of the formal contract for measuring supply is analogous to the use of formal business planning in order to achieve strategic goals, whereby it is difficult to relate formal contract, or plan, measurement as the business environment changes. An adaptive persistence approach that address issues flexibly through better communication and interaction may prove more successful. Gibb⁴² stated, when discussing the competitiveness of small businesses that do not rely on formal relationships, contracts and plans that,

Excessive focus on the plan, particularly if it was used rigorously for monitoring and control by third parties, may inhibit entrepreneurial response to changes in the environment. Facing up to the fact that business plans are but one (formal) way of exploring a new development before embarking upon it and alternatively are of value to a bank manager or bureaucrat as his/her own personal risk reduction document is important. Real success and learning priorities lie with how well the firm responds flexibly to customers, **suppliers** and key players in the network as it develops. It is scarcely surprising that it is difficult to relate formal planning to business success

Rich and Hines⁴³ describe this approach as"The collaborative relationship management approach", whereby the organisation... "seeks to extend the formal exchange process between trading organizations to create an informal contract to supply. This can be regarded as a strategy deliberately to socialize suppliers to the norms and goals of the focal organization, such that traditional methods of control can be replaced by the exchange of influence and co-determination of

the supply chain. A common goal in this process is the profitability and longevity of the trading relationship. In this process of socialization, the demonstration or perception of benefits between companies is important if the relationship approach is to be relayed, by suppliers, to lower levels of the material supply chain."

Other researchers such as Knill, et al⁴⁴ propose to re-engineer supply chain management processes altogether and instead adopt what they refer to as supply chain synthesis, where active partnerships are engendered between suppliers and purchasers and the formal contract has little relevance and the flow of information and measurement is based on a collaborative, although to some extent still contractually measured, relationship.

Understanding SCS partnerships. Conventional 'partnerships' still involve competitive bidding, multiple sources, adversarial relationships, etc. Those partnerships don't work in supply chain situations. A supply chain synthesis partnership has to evolve into a long-term relationship based on trust and true understanding of SCS. Sharing of information, planning, scheduling, risk, rewards, problems, solutions, opportunities for creating peak-to-peak performance - all these are components of an SCS partnership. Keep in mind that you can't build a partnership in a couple of half-hour meetings. Participants have to get to know each other, to determine how deep or shallow a relationship will be developed.

The response to the questionnaire also showed that the formal contract had no discernible impact on the purchasing professionals perception of the ease of business with the supplier. This would suggest that whilst the formal contract is a record of the agreement and a measure of the physical properties of supply, it does not, as a continual metric of that supply increase the ease of the business relationship, nor does it

increase the chance of success of the supply relationship. In fact a reliance on the supply contract as a formal measure may well decrease the effectiveness and ease of the supplier purchaser relationship in that it may well reduce the real interaction between the two groups to an adversarial set of measures and contract waving.

This and the findings from the questionnaire support the second hypothesis of this thesis that, ***the formal contract, and tangible procedures such as TQM, as a form of physical measurement have little impact on the ease of business and the success of the supply relationship.***

7.7.3. H-3: The Ease of Relationship as Directly Related to the Skills and Knowledge Base of the Supplier

Takeuchi⁴⁵ defines 'knowledge creation' as innovation that is systematic and continuous. Sherman⁴⁶, when interviewing Takeuchi, and discussing the differences in tacit (implicit) and explicit knowledge as applied to both US and Japanese business cultures, commented that

...each culture is most comfortable with only one. In the U.S., people are very comfortable with explicit knowledge, the sort of information that can be verbalized, written down in documents, put into computers, and readily communicated. The Japanese don't do that very well. They're best at tapping tacit knowledge, which comes from personal experience and is usually difficult to express. It's what you feel in your gut when you have a hunch or an inspiration. It's not purely rational. Tacit knowledge is connected to emotions, beliefs--it's more a bodily knowledge than something in the mind. Americans aren't as comfortable with that. Creating knowledge requires a convergence of tacit and explicit knowledge. There has to be a spiral from one type of knowledge to the other, and back again.

The knowledge base of the supplier is important, the results to the questionnaire show that the majority of purchasing practitioners believe this and that also they feel that ease of business increases the more they have confidence in, and recognise the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier. This does not mean however that if the skills of the supplier are good and they have years of knowledge relating to

the item of supply or service the supply relationship will necessarily be good automatically. The real metric of the argument is the level of recognition and confidence and therefore assumed interdependency between the two organisations. Gibb⁴⁷ argued that while these concepts of stakeholder and network interdependency may be relatively new to the large company they arguably form the basic ground rules for survival and growth of the small business. The very essence of small company management is the personal day-to-day handling of transactional and other relationships with the network of customers, suppliers, bankers, accountants, solicitors, agents, marketing channels, workers and regulatory authorities as well as, more intimately, acquaintances, friends and family. Thus, the key to success of the small business might be said to be that of managing and developing this network of interdependency under conditions of, more or less, uncertainty. In the absence, usually, of dominant power in the marketplace the small firm attempts to reduce the risks associated with uncertainty by building personal relationships of trust and confidence with its key stakeholders. Its ability to survive will be a function of its ability to learn from these stakeholders, to educate these stakeholders, to build trust and interdependency with these stakeholders, to use them to scan the wider business environment and to define, meet and bring forward their future needs.

It is this interdependency that can be judged as lacking in the larger more established business, where professional purchasing practices and layers of personnel lie between the purchaser and providers.

By having confidence in the skills and knowledge base of the supplier the organisation is able to work with that supplier, the survey shows that there is a high degree of correlation at

operational, tactical and strategic levels relating to the degree of confidence, and the perception of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier with the perceived ease of transaction and business.

This relates to the skills and knowledge grid as proposed earlier in this thesis, the grid directly relates the balance of power between the two organisations, purchaser and supplier.

Skills and Knowledge of Supplier

		High	Low
Skills and Knowledge of customer	High	1	2
	Low	3	4

In relationships where there is a high level of interdependency and organisational learning, i.e. the purchaser has the recognition of and the confidence in the suppliers skills and knowledge base the relationship will occupy box 1. This relationship is more likely to result in successful supply, shown in the questionnaire data analysis than a relationship where the purchaser has little confidence in the skills and knowledge of the supplier, either box 2 or box 3.

Piercy made the point about relationship as a strategy, in the wider context of marketing, when he said,

The new era is one where many of the traditional rules of competition with which we are familiar and comfortable are being replaced by collaboration, alliance and new forms of network or 'hollow' organisation. Relationship marketing has become a dominant approach in many consumer markets and *partnering has replaced many traditional buyer-seller relationships in industrial markets*. Alliances have become the basis for competition in industries like airlines and telecommunications. Supply chain collaborations are replacing traditional relationships between competitors and distributors.

There has been a fundamental shift in inter-organisational relationships which cannot be underestimated in its importance. Not all organisations will partner with others, but in many industries collaborations will radically alter the competitive realities faced. Understanding our organisations will increasingly depend on analysing the underlying relationship structure.

The underlying rationale for the hypothesis still stands and is supported by the data gathered through the survey and through the literature consulted, that:

Purchaser confidence in, and acknowledgement of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier, the interaction between the parties and the confidence in the information received is directly related to the perceived ease of the supply relationship.

7.7.4. H-4: The Impact of the Frequency and Quality of Interaction Between the Purchaser and Supplier on the Ease of Business.

The data analysis shows that with a TQM programme in place and a reported high level of interaction between the supplier and the purchaser that the perceived ease of business increases, this is also true for companies that operate joint multidisciplinary teams. However the data showed that the frequency of these meetings has little impact on the perceived ease of the business relationship. An expected result might be that at the operational level the meetings would show an influence at a regular frequency and at the tactical and strategic levels the frequency would be less, due to the complexity and nature of the relationship, but still show an influence on the perceived ease of business.

This prompts the argument that as the data, background study and focus group work has shown that interaction and communication through multidisciplinary team working does contribute to the success of the business relationship, but the frequency of these meetings does not - even at the operational level, then it is the quality of the communication and the inter personal relations that build up through this inter-organisational contact that is responsible for the increased incidence of successful supply / purchaser relations.

This is borne out by the work of Trent⁴⁸ where in discussing cross functional teams and their role in sourcing he determined that,

when executed properly, the cross-functional team approach can bring together the knowledge and

resources required for responding to new sourcing demands, something traditional functional structures are often incapable of doing. However, in a classic work 35 years ago, Likert⁴⁹ noted that groups and teams can accomplish much that is good, or they can do great harm. There is nothing implicitly good or bad, weak or strong, about teams, regardless of where an organization uses them.

This again, along with the findings from the questionnaire, point to the argument that it is not the team structure itself or how often they meet, but it is the knowledge they bring and the way they communicate with each other that enhances the probability of success. Mangaliso⁵⁰ showed that "in the case of gathering information, it is not just the quantity of information that is of importance but also the degree of richness of the information necessary to enhance management co-ordination and control"

Therefore, ***The frequency of interaction between the purchaser and supplier does not directly impinge on the ease of business, but rather it is the quality of interaction increases the ease of business and the potential success of the supply relationship.***

8. Conclusions & Recommendations

Conformance to procedure and specification has little impact on the perceived ease of business with the suppliers. This does not mean to say that if these physical factors were uncontrolled that the ease of business relations would be unaffected, but that this element of the business relationship is well within the control of the purchasing professionals

Physical aspects of the supply chain such as delivery performance, price and quality whilst being vital to good manufacturing and service provision are given factors and are not responsible for the perceived ease of business with the supplier, and the success of the supply relationship.

The formal contract had no discernible impact on the purchasing professionals perception of the ease of business with the supplier. This would suggest that whilst the formal contract is a record of the agreement and a measure of the physical properties of supply, it does not, as a continual metric of that supply increase the ease of the business relationship, nor does it increase the chance of success of the supply relationship. In fact a reliance on the supply contract as a formal measure may well decrease the effectiveness and ease of the supplier purchaser relationship in that it may well reduce the real interaction between the two groups to an adversarial set of measures and contract waving.

This and the findings from the questionnaire support the second hypothesis of this thesis that, **the formal contract, and tangible procedures such as TQM, as a form of physical measurement have little impact on the ease of business and the success of the supply relationship.**

By having confidence in the skills and knowledge base of the supplier the

organisation is able to work with that supplier, the survey shows that there is a high degree of correlation at operational, tactical and strategic levels relating to the degree of confidence, and the perception of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier with the perceived ease of transaction and business.

This relates to the skills and knowledge grid as proposed earlier in this thesis, the grid directly relates the balance of power between the two organisations, purchaser and supplier.

Purchaser confidence in, and acknowledgement of the importance of, the skills and knowledge base of the supplier, the interaction between the parties and the confidence in the information received is directly related to the perceived ease of the supply relationship.

The data analysis shows that with a TQM programme in place and a reported high level of interaction between the supplier and the purchaser that the perceived ease of business increases, this is also true for companies that operate joint multidisciplinary teams. However the data showed that the frequency of these meetings has little impact on the perceived ease of the business relationship.

it is the quality of the communication and the inter personal relations that build up through inter-organisational contact that is responsible for the increased incidence of successful supply / purchaser relations.

The frequency of interaction between the purchaser and supplier does not directly impinge on the ease of business, but rather it is the quality of interaction increases the ease of business and the potential success of the supply relationship.

This thesis would recommend that whilst an investigation has been made into the importance of intangible factors that this work be built upon by investigating:

The ways in which purchasers define 'ease of transaction' and how this can be further engendered through 'quality of information, or quality of transaction'.

Also it is recommended that specific attempts are made to investigate situations closely resembling the hypotheses above in order to gain additional data that would assist in imposing measurable factors upon the intangible, but beneficial, elements of transaction discussed above.

Andrew Bell

31st August 1999

9. References

1. Keith Goffin, Marek Szwajkowski, Colin New , "Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)
2. C. M. Harland, "Supply chain management - relationships, chains and networks", British Journal of Management, Vol. 7, Special Issue, March 1996, pp. S63-S80.
3. Karel van Donselaar; Graham Sharman, "An innovative survey in the transportation and distribution sector. (Survey Research in Operations Management)", International Journal of Operations & Production Management, July-August 1997 v17 n7-8 p707(14)
4. Anita Van de Vliet, "To beat the best. (benchmarking)", Management Today, Jan 1996 p56(5),
5. Doug Bartholomew, "The supply chain's value-add. (reflections on current state of supply chain management in industry)"(Editorial), Industry Week, Feb 2, 1998 v247 n3 p36(1)
6. Taylor, F.W. (1911), *The Principles of Scientific Management*, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
7. "Supply-chain management and time-based competition: the role of the supplier", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, March-April 1997 v27 n3-4 p210(16)
8. Farmer, D. (1995), "Purchasing myopia - a touch of Mr Magoo", Proceedings for the First World-wide Research Symposium on Purchasing and Supply Chain Management, Arizona State University, Phoenix, AZ,

pp. 63-71.

9. John T. Landry, "Supply Chain Management." Harvard Business Review, Nov 1, 1998 p24(1),
10. Rick Mullin, "Knowledge management: a cultural evolution. (Dow Chemical Co)", Journal of Business Strategy, Sep-Oct 1996 v17 n5 p56(4)
11. Paul C. Ballman, "Managing effectively in chaos, (personnel management)", Human Resource Planning, Sep 1996 v19 n3 p11(4),
12. Rosabeth Moss Kanter , "Can giants dance in cyberspace? (large companies and the Internet"; Public Life; Forbes ASAP), Forbes, Dec 2, 1996 v158 n13 pS247(2),
13. Keith Goffin; Mark Szwejcowski; "Colin New, Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15),
14. Kolay, M.K., "Suppliers asset base - appreciating or depreciating?", International Journal of Operations & Production Management, Vol. 13 No. 8, 1993, pp. 72-86.
15. Monczka, R.M., Callahan, T.J. and Nichols, E.L., "Predictors of relationships among buying and supplying firms", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 25 No. 10, 1995, pp. 45-59.
16. Ellram, L.M., "The supplier selection decision in strategic partnerships", Journal of Purchasing and Materials Management, Vol. 26 No. 4, 1990, pp. 8-14.
17. Leenders, M.R., Nollet, J. and Ellram, L.M., "Adapting purchasing to supply chain management", International Journal of Physical Distribution &

- Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 1, 1994, pp. 40-2.
18. Burt, D.N., "Managing supplies up to speed", Harvard Business Review, Vol. 67 No. 4, 1989, pp. 127-35.
19. Harland, C.M., "Supply chain management - relationships, chains and networks", British Journal of Management, Vol. 7, Special Issue, March 1996, pp.S63-S80.
20. Jacky Holloway; Graham Francis; Matthew Hinton; David Mayle, "Best practice benchmarking: delivering the goods? (Proceedings of the 3rd World Congress for Total Quality Management Business Excellence Through Quality Culture)", Total Quality Management, July 1998 v9 n4-5 pS121(5)
21. "First find your bench ", The Economist, May 11, 1991 v319 n7706 p72(1).
22. Mzamo P. Mangaliso, "The strategic usefulness of management information as perceived by middle managers", Journal of Management, Summer 1995 v21 n2 p231(20),
23. Proctor, R.A. (1991). "Marketing information systems". Management Decision, 29(4): 55-60.
24. Christian Cull, "Let's talk about us. (Tesco PLC, relationship with its suppliers)(The Grocer focus on Tesco supplement.)", Grocer, Sep 20, 1997 v220 n7323 pS12(2),
25. Keith Goffin; Marek Szwajkowski; Colin New, "Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)
26. Mohanty, R.P. and Deshmukh, S.G., "Use of analytic hierarchic process for evaluating sources of supply", International Journal of Physical

- Distribution & Logistics, Vol. 23 No. 3, 1993, pp. 22-8.
27. Lee, H. and Wellan, D.M., "Vendor survey plan: a selection strategy for JIT/TQM Suppliers", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 23 No. 7, 1993, pp. 39-45.
28. Larson, P.D., "Buyer-supplier co-operation, product quality and total costs", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 6, 1994, pp. 4-9.
29. Harrison, A., "Co-makership as an extension of quality care", International Journal Quality & Reliability Management, Vol. 7 No. 2, 1990, pp. 15-22.
30. Mohanty, R.P. and Deshmukh, S.G., "Use of analytic hierarchic process for evaluating sources of supply", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics, Vol. 23 No. 3, 1993, pp. 22-8.
31. Levy, P., Bessant, J., Sang, B. and Lamming, R., "Developing integration through total quality supply chain management", Integrated Manufacturing Systems. Vol. 6 No. 3, 1995, pp. 4-12.
32. Larson, P.D., "Buyer-supplier co-operation, product quality and total costs", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 6, 1994, pp. 4-9.
33. Larson, P.D., "Buyer-supplier co-operation, product quality and total costs", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 6, 1994, pp. 4-9.
34. Harrison, A., "Co-makership as an extension of quality care", International Journal Quality & Reliability Management, Vol. 7 No. 2, 1990, pp. 15-22.
35. Turnbull, P., Delridge, R, Oliver, N. and Wilkinson, B., "Winners and losers - the 'tiering' of component suppliers in the UK automotive industry",

- Journal of General Management. Vol. 19 No. 1, 1993, pp. 48-63.
36. Merlyn, V. and Parkinson, J. (1994), *Development Effectiveness: Strategies for IS Organisational Transition*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY.
37. Monica Parzinger; Narendra Ramarapu; E. Timmerman, "A stage-wise application of total quality management through the product life cycle" Industrial Management & Data Systems, March-April 1997 v97 n3-4 p125(6)
38. Powell, T.C. (1995), "Total quality management as competitive advantage: a review and empirical study", Strategic Management Journal, Vol. 16, pp. 15-37.
39. Stan Glaser, "Management duckspeak. (meaningless terms used in management)", Management Decision, Sept-Oct 1997 v35 n9-10 p649(3)
40. Nick Rich; Peter Hines, "Supply-chain management and time-based competition: the role of the supplier association", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, March-April 1997 v27 n3-4 p210(16)
41. Stevens, G. (1989), "Integrating the supply chain", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Materials Management, Vol. 19 No. 8, pp. 3-8.
42. Allan A. Gibb, "Small firms' training and competitiveness. Building upon the small business as a learning organisation", International Small Business Journal, April-June 1997 v15 n3 p13(17)
43. Nick Rich; Peter Hines, "Supply-chain management and time-based competition: the role of the supplier association", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, March-April 1997 v27 n3-4

p210(16)

44. James A.; Knill Tompkins Bernie; Andel Tom, "Time To Rise Above Supply Chain Management.", Transportation & Distribution, Oct 1, 1998 pSC16
45. Takeuchi, H. and Nonaka, I., "The new new product development game", Harvard Business Review, Vol. 64 No. 1, January-February 1986, pp. 137-46.
46. Stratford Sherman, Hot products from hot tubs, or how managers innovate. Hirotaka Takeuchi, author of 'The Knowledge-Creating Company: How Japanese Companies Create the Dynamics of Innovation')(Interview), Fortune, April 29, 1996 v133 n8 p165(3)
47. Allan A. Gibb, "Small firms' training and competitiveness. Building upon the small business as a learning organisation", International Small Business Journal, April-June 1997 v15 n3 p13(17)
48. Robert J. Trent, "Understanding and evaluating cross-functional sourcing team leadership", International Journal of Purchasing and Materials Management, Fall 1996 v32 n4 p29(8)
49. R. Likert, *New Patterns of Management* (New York McGraw-Hill, 1961), p. 162.
50. Mzamo P. Mangaliso, "The strategic usefulness of management information as perceived by middle managers", Journal of Management, Summer 1995 v21 n2 p231(20)
51. Keith Goffin; Marek Szwajczewski; Colin New, "Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)

52. Harland, C.M., "Supply chain management - relationships, chains and networks", British Journal of Management, Vol. 7, Special Issue, March 1996, pp. S63-S80.
53. Karel van Donselaar; Graham Sharman, "An innovative survey in the transportation and distribution sector. (Survey Research in Operations Management) ", International Journal of Operations & Production Management, July-August 1997 v17 n7-8 p707(14)

Appendix 1: Lawrence and Galati's Four Pillars

Power Balancing. Instead of using their buying leverage to extract concessions from small suppliers, purchasing managers balance their contracts so that neither manufacturer nor supplier is highly dependent on the other. One manager, for example, said he aimed to procure between 20% and 40% of the company's total requirements for a part from any given supplier, and he liked to see suppliers shipping about the same percentage of their total output to his company. Such power balancing does more than make suppliers feel less vulnerable; it also helps the manufacturer. Suppliers become more innovative as they work with and learn from other customers, and the manufacturer reaps the benefits of the suppliers' greater creativity. Perhaps even more important, power balancing helps create a new mind-set among managers from both sides, replacing the old dynamics of power and domination with a trusting, consultative relationship.

Co-specialisation. As they try to balance power, purchasing managers also try to achieve a degree of mutual dependence in their alliances. A supplier might have a factory make parts that work exclusively in one car model, or the carmaker might adapt one of its assembly lines to fit a particular supplier's needs. Often, a manufacturer will anoint "preferred suppliers" for a particular component, which encourages them to move beyond manufacturing and contribute to the design and engineering of components. When suppliers and purchasers both devote substantial resources to their relationship, each stands to lose a great deal from jeopardising it. As both parties recognise the close intertwining of their fates and the futility of seeking short-term gains at the other's expense, their focus shifts to building trust and seeking mutually beneficial outcomes.

Target Costing. The co-operative approach extends to pricing as well. Instead of the adversarial system of competitive bidding for contracts, the purchasing managers set target costs based on the manufacturer's goal for the final selling price of the car. By communicating a target cost for a component early in the development process-and by sharing any gains from delivering components below the target cost - they encourage suppliers to engage in joint problem solving, leading to more efficient design and production.

Personal Ties. The most trusting alliances, Lawrence and Galati found, are also built at the individual level. Personal ties among managers are often what keeps alliances productive. The establishment of joint teams to solve problems, for example, not only improves the flow of information but also encourages each side to feel comfortable with the other. Personal bonds, developed gradually, strengthen the partners' commitment to honest dealing, freeing them from the need for cumbersome legal arrangements.

Appendix 2: The Questionnaire

1. Objectives

The objective of the questionnaire is to establish the relevance and importance of the intangible factors that influence the Supplier/Customer relationship and impact on Supplier performance as it is normally measured using tangible evidence.

2. Background and Output

The Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply receive many calls a month about evaluating suppliers and measuring their performance. In response to members needs, in this area of professional practice, the Institute in partnership with Coventry University Business School has initiated new research in this very important area. The questionnaire is based on an analysis of current practice, leading edge thinking, and the output from two focus groups.

Your input in answering this questionnaire will play a vital role in shaping the future of Supplier evaluation, the setting of supplier performance standards, and their measurement.

3. Notes on the content of the questionnaire

- 3.1 Section 1 – questions 1-6 deal with data that describes your company, the purchasing department and its role. “Mission Critical” relates to goods and/or services purchased that are used directly in the core business operations. Subsidiary purchases relate to goods and/or services purchased that support the overall operation of the business in general.
- 3.2 Section 2 – Question 7 –9 deal current supplier performance as measured through tangible factors. Delivery in terms of time and quantity: Quality in terms of performance of product or service actually purchased and Price year on year in terms of increasing value for money.
- 3.3 Section 3 – Questions 10 – 15 deal with three intangible areas, Skills, Knowledge and Information. A definition for skill is provided prior to question 10 and a definition for knowledge provided prior to question 12. The questions on Skills and Knowledge have three subsidiary areas: -
- Operational Level** refers to the day to day activities of a company that generate the products and/or services supplied to the market. It includes short-term decisions made on a daily basis that adjust and fine-tune those activities. This can be evidenced in terms of responsiveness.
- Tactical Level** refers to the managerial and supervisory

activities that lead to the control and perhaps reallocation of resources to ensure that the tasks and processes at the operational level are effective and efficient. This can be evidenced in terms establishing a potential for responsiveness.

- refers to a long term planning horizon that deals with the characteristics of the supplier/customer relationship, boundaries of responsibility, i.e. decisions on issues that affect both companies at the corporate level.

- 3.4 Section 4 – Questions 16 – 22 deal with the activities taking place at the interface between customers and suppliers. These deal with joint activities entered into to: Firstly ensure overall efficiency in the processes: Secondly to monitor and adjust processes to improve effectiveness and: Thirdly to analyse processes with a radical viewpoint for long term planning.

May we thank you in advance for helping in this important research that will help the Institute to expand its services to members.

Supplier Assessment Questionnaire

Section 1 - About your company

<p>1. How many people are employed by your organisation?</p>	<p>Please tick appropriate box.</p>	<table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">0-200</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">201-500</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">501 plus</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> </table>	0-200		201-500		501 plus			
0-200										
201-500										
501 plus										
<p>2. How many people work in the purchasing department? include clerical staff</p>	<p>Please tick appropriate box</p>	<table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">0-5</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">6-15</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">16 plus</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> </table>	0-5		6-15		16 plus			
0-5										
6-15										
16 plus										
<p>3. Which one of the categories describes your company's industrial sector best?</p>	<p>Please tick only one box</p>	<table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Extraction</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Manufacturing</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Retail and Wholesale</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Services including Distribution</td> <td style="width: 40px; height: 30px;"></td> </tr> </table>	Extraction		Manufacturing		Retail and Wholesale		Services including Distribution	
Extraction										
Manufacturing										
Retail and Wholesale										
Services including Distribution										

The following questions are about “mission critical” purchases and the subsidiary purchases.

4. Which of the following categories describes the “mission critical” purchasing areas best

You may tick more than one box

Production items	
Consumables or Maintenance & Repair items. MRO	
Capital Equipment	
Goods for resale	
Services	

5. Which of the following categories describes the subsidiary purchasing areas best

You may tick more than one box

Production items	
Consumables or Maintenance & Repair items. MRO	
Capital Equipment	
Goods for resale	
Services	

6. What is your average annual spend on “mission critical” items?

£ _____

The following questions apply only to suppliers within your “mission critical” purchase areas, as specified in question 4

Section 2 – Current Supplier Performance

7. Overall, our suppliers meet the delivery service standards we expect

To what extent do you agree with this statement?

Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree, to 5=strongly agree

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

--	--	--	--	--

8. Overall, our suppliers meet the Product/Service quality standards we expect.

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

1	2	3	4	5

9. Overall, our suppliers meet the price performance targets we expect

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree, to 5=strongly agree

1	2	3	4	5

Section 3 – Skills, Knowledge and Information

The following question is about the skills bases of your “mission critical” suppliers. A skill is defined as “ a craft or accomplishment, aptitude and competencies appropriate for a particular job”. Most importantly the necessary skills applied in the operational activities of the business at all levels. Other skills can be “communication”, both written and oral; project management skills, meeting skills, and general inter-personal skills.

10. The skills bases of our “mission critical” suppliers are an important component of the business relationship, at the:

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational level					
Tactical level					
Strategic level					

11. Overall, my company has confidence in the skill bases of its “mission critical” suppliers, at the:

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational level					
Tactical level					
Strategic level					

The following question is about the knowledge base of your “mission critical” suppliers. Knowledge, defined in the context of the organisation, is about the ability to draw together; the practical skills, (as defined for questions 10 and 11); internally generated and externally generated information, and the combination of learning by experience and formal learning, so that an organisation can adapt, develop mutually beneficial relationships with the external environment and prosper

12. The knowledge bases of our “mission critical” suppliers are an important component of the business relationship, at the:

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational level					
Tactical level					
Strategic level					

13. Overall, my company has confidence in the knowledge bases of its “mission critical” suppliers, at the:

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational level					
Tactical level					
Strategic level					

14. Overall, our company has confidence in the information received from its suppliers

To what extent do you agree with this statement?

Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

1	2	3	4	5

15. Overall, the Purchasing Department has confidence in the information generated within our company.

To what extent do you agree with this statement?

Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

1	2	3	4	5

Section 4 – Customer/Supplier Interface Activities

16. To what extent does your company interact with its “mission critical” suppliers? at the:

high level

On a scale of 1-5, where 1 = low level to 5=

Operational level
Tactical level
Strategic level

1	2	3	4	5

17. Does your company have a Total Quality Management programme that includes the “mission critical” suppliers in co-ordinated “continuous improvement programmes”?

Ye	No

18. Does your company operate joint multi-disciplinary teams with its “mission critical” suppliers that meet on a regular basis? at the:

	Ye	No
Operational level		
Tactical level		
Strategic level		

19. What are the frequency of these joint meetings with suppliers? at the:

1=Weekly, 2=Monthly, 3=every 3 months, 4=half yearly, 5=yearly

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational level					
Tactical level					
Strategic level					

20. Overall, our company is confident that the “mission critical” suppliers will meet their obligations arising from the joint meetings at the

To what extent do you agree with this statement?
Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

	1	2	3	4	5
Operational level					
Tactical level					
Strategic level					

21. How easy is it to do business with the company’s “mission critical suppliers” suppliers?

On a scale of 1-5, where 1=difficult to 5=easy

1	2	3	4	5

22. Our company always uses the formal contract with the supplier, as the basis for measuring the performance of that particular company.

To what extent do you agree with this statement?

Please mark on the scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

1	2	3	4	5

Appendix 3: Cross Tabulation of Skills and Knowledge Data

Q10i. Operational Level

Skill_imp_Com_OP_10 counts	Know_Supp_OP_12					Know_Supp_TC_12					Know_Supp_ST_12					Know_Conf_OP_13					Know_Conf_TC_13					Know_Conf_ST_13										
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Total					
2	0	2	3	2	0	0	0	1	5	1	0	0	0	1	3	3	0	0	0	1	5	1	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	1	5	1	0	7
3	0	1	13	11	3	0	0	4	10	11	3	0	1	3	9	10	5	0	0	3	15	9	1	0	0	3	20	4	1	0	1	5	15	6	1	28
4	0	1	21	70	15	1	1	2	29	56	18	0	1	3	31	45	27	0	2	7	38	53	7	1	3	10	40	50	3	0	3	14	38	46	6	107
5	1	1	6	26	77	1	0	1	15	43	51	1	0	3	18	36	53	1	1	3	26	55	25	1	1	8	37	49	15	1	1	13	44	39	13	111
Total	1	5	43	109	95	2	1	8	59	111	72	1	2	10	61	94	85	1	3	14	84	118	33	2	4	21	104	103	19	1	5	33	102	92	20	253
Contingency coefficient	0.584					0.431					0.332					0.342					0.353					0.236										

coefficient contingency total	0.584					0.431					0.332					0.342					0.353					0.236										
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	
4	0	1	21	70	15	1	1	2	29	56	18	0	1	3	31	45	27	0	2	7	38	53	7	1	3	10	40	50	3	0	3	14	38	46	6	107
5	1	1	6	26	77	1	0	1	15	43	51	1	0	3	18	36	53	1	1	3	26	55	25	1	1	8	37	49	15	1	1	13	44	39	13	111
contingency coefficient	0.584					0.431					0.332					0.342					0.353					0.236										

Q10i. Operational Level

coefficient contingency total	0.584					0.431					0.332					0.342					0.353					0.236										
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	0	1	13	11	3	
4	0	1	21	70	15	1	1	2	29	56	18	0	1	3	31	45	27	0	2	7	38	53	7	1	3	10	40	50	3	0	3	14	38	46	6	107
5	1	1	6	26	77	1	0	1	15	43	51	1	0	3	18	36	53	1	1	3	26	55	25	1	1	8	37	49	15	1	1	13	44	39	13	111
contingency coefficient	0.584					0.431					0.332					0.342					0.353					0.236										

Q10ii. Strategic Level

Skill Conf. ST_11 counts	Know_Supp_OP_12					Know_Supp_TC_12					Know_Supp_ST_12					Know_Conf_OP_13					Know_Conf_TC_13					Know_Conf_ST_13					Total	
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5		
Not answered	1	0	1	1	2	1	0	0	1	3	0	1	0	0	2	2	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	2	0	5
1	0	0	2	2	2	0	1	1	2	2	0	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	3	2	0	1	0	6	
2	0	3	10	11	11	0	0	4	12	11	8	0	0	8	8	10	9	0	1	3	18	9	4	0	0	1	11	19	4	0	35	
3	0	1	15	47	34	0	0	2	28	43	24	0	0	1	33	40	23	0	0	8	42	39	8	0	0	4	61	29	3	0	97	
4	0	1	14	39	34	1	0	1	16	43	27	0	0	0	16	37	35	0	0	1	19	59	9	1	0	3	22	57	5	0	88	
5	0	0	1	9	12	0	0	0	0	9	13	0	0	0	1	5	16	0	0	1	1	8	11	0	0	0	1	10	11	0	22	
Total	1	5	43	109	95	2	1	8	59	111	72	1	2	10	61	94	85	1	3	14	84	118	33	2	4	21	104	103	19	1	253	
Contingency coefficient	0.464					0.537					0.666					0.581					0.714					0.770						

Q11ii. Strategic Level

Skill Conf. ST_11 counts	Know_Supp_OP_12					Know_Supp_TC_12					Know_Supp_ST_12					Know_Conf_OP_13					Know_Conf_TC_13					Know_Conf_ST_13					Total	
	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5	Not answered	1	2	3	4	5		
Not answered	1	0	1	1	2	1	0	0	1	3	0	1	0	0	2	2	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	2	0	5
1	0	0	2	2	2	0	1	1	2	2	0	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	3	2	0	1	0	6	
2	0	3	10	11	11	0	0	4	12	11	8	0	0	8	8	10	9	0	1	3	18	9	4	0	0	1	11	19	4	0	35	
3	0	1	15	47	34	0	0	2	28	43	24	0	0	1	33	40	23	0	0	8	42	39	8	0	0	4	61	29	3	0	97	
4	0	1	14	39	34	1	0	1	16	43	27	0	0	0	16	37	35	0	0	1	19	59	9	1	0	3	22	57	5	0	88	
5	0	0	1	9	12	0	0	0	0	9	13	0	0	0	1	5	16	0	0	1	1	8	11	0	0	0	1	10	11	0	22	
Total	1	5	43	109	95	2	1	8	59	111	72	1	2	10	61	94	85	1	3	14	84	118	33	2	4	21	104	103	19	1	253	
Contingency coefficient	0.464					0.537					0.666					0.581					0.714					0.770						

Q11iii. Strategic Level

Q11iii. Strategic Level

Appendix 4: Synthesis Report from Focus Group Meetings

1) Introduction

This report represents a progress summary and initial synthesis of data obtained during two focus group meetings for the supplier performance benchmarking study performed through Coventry University and the Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply (CIPS).

The purpose of this report is to allow the research team, consisting of:

Brian Jeffery: Coventry University;
Andrew Bell: Nullifire Limited;
Carl Kochelbergh: CIPS,

to evaluate the data collected so far and to develop an industry relevant questionnaire that will take forward an overall understanding of the subject of supplier performance benchmarking.

2) Terms of Reference

In collating the data analysed within this report two focus group meetings were held and a literature review, detailing current thinking regarding supplier performance benchmarking, was conducted. The findings of the meetings are presented in Appendix 1 and 2 in the form of short meeting reports. The initial literature review is also contained within the appendices.

3) Findings

The Initial Literature Review

The initial literature review showed that the actual processes used

within industry and the service sector was based largely around given quantifiable factors. Goffin⁵¹ found in a 1997 study of supplier base reduction that “Most of the criteria for supplier choice are focused on quantifiable measures; however, other more qualitative factors need to be considered. For example, an assessment needs to be made of whether the culture of the supplier's organisation can co-operate effectively with the buyer's organisational culture.⁵²”. This applies even to large scale pieces of research work such as the ‘BRAVO’ benchmarking study carried out in the Netherlands⁵³.

The quantifiable factors are often judged on a speculative scoring basis by staff within the purchasers organisation. This whilst obviously being subject to operator bias requires a historical perspective on the relationship. The speculative score based systems are not appropriate for benchmarking new suppliers and relatively little literature exists on this subject.

The Focus Groups

Group 1 – Technology, Industry and Manufacturing

Group 1 is as listed in the report contained within the Appendix.

The themes explored during the focus group were:

- Objectives of transaction
- Complexity of transaction
- Tangible benefits
- Intangible benefits
- Process control
- Information exchange

The summary of the findings of the focus group indicated that with

reference to intangible elements this is the area in which it seems that purchasers rely to the main extent on 'gut feel'. The other elements of the transaction, both pre and post transaction are largely based on the individual perspective of the purchaser and their relationship with the supplier. It is this area which the purchasing professionals found hardest to quantify. However it is this area which defines, for example, the management of the supplier and their intellectual ability to manage the transaction in order to ensure that the relationship is a successful one. In many cases the purchasing professional represented cannot effectively judge or manage the suppliers' ability to maintain a relationship or manage the supply process. This is the element of culture that in common with business mergers, possibly the closest other inter business relationship to supply agreements, means that a large percentage of supply agreements can be judged as being unsuccessful.

Group 2 – Service, Financial and IT Industry

The summary of the findings for the second focus group showed that whilst these industry sectors did tend to evaluate new supplier on a more historically relevant basis, by industry referencing that the level of unsatisfactory buyer / supplier relationships was largely the same as the previous industry focus group. Again the given factors could be quantified, however the 'softer' factors were very much based on a historical perspective with existing suppliers, i.e. was the relationship good or not. With new suppliers, again, this could not be quantified and as such was largely a matter of 'gut feel' based around the buyers perception of the supplier.

4) Areas to be Explored

In examining the findings from the initial literature review and the focus groups we can see several relationships. These are illustrated in the form of models in Figures 1 and 2.

(These models are included in the main text of the report, and as such have been omitted from this earlier report)

Figure 1 shows the relationship between the skills and knowledge of the supplier and the skills and knowledge of the customer. It also gives us an insight into the potential success of or failure of the relationship. For example if the skills and knowledge of both the supplier and customer the relationship will have little field expertise on which to be founded and is likely to be unsuccessful. If one of the participants in the relationship is highly skilled in the area in which the supply relationship is to be conducted then the relationship has a better chance of success. If the supplier and customer both are highly skilled in the area in which the relationship is conducted then the relationship should, theoretically, stand a higher chance of resulting in a successful supply partnership. There may however be cases where the joint expertise actually leads to conflict.

In Figure 2 the nine box model indicates a relationship between, and a method of defining both customers and suppliers skills levels relevant to the transaction.

In determining areas to be addressed in the questionnaire it seems that as a group the research team have to identify questions that will address the less well defined relationship factors within the supplier / customer transaction. This especially applies to new suppliers where these factors remain largely unknown and subject to only speculative judgement.

Appendix 5: Stevens Four Stages in the Evolutionary Process of Restructuring

Stevens (1989) identifies four stages in this evolutionary process of restructuring:

(1) The baseline organization. This organization operates the classical system of management, with the motivation of profit maximisation and a high level of functional specialisation. The company cannot adapt quickly to changes in the consumer market and has a low ability to exploit materials flow or market information.

(2) The functionally integrated company. This organization has begun to erode the hierarchical structure and short-term financial focus by concentrating on customer service criteria and sales order processing. The major competitive advantage of this organization is in the distribution efficiency of the system and the collaboration between the sales function and the distribution function.

(3) The internally integrated company. This organization has continued to restructure and align the activities of manufacturing and purchasing to create a systems approach to customer service. The company has reduced the number of administrative functions required and operates effective interfaces between departments to optimise information exchange and hence the overall performance of the company. The planning horizon has also extended from the short term to the medium term and involves a limited interaction with suppliers. At this point the organisational structure may become product-focused and involve a high level of cross-functional management.

(4) The externally integrated company. This organisational state involves the externalisation of the alignment process and the integration of the supply base with the demands of the consumer in a transparent system of materials and information exchange. The

company seeks deliberately to manage the interfaces between companies to generate a flexible and responsive system of long-term collaboration. At this point the company has completed the restructuring of its internal supply-chain and has recognised the importance of external supply-chain management strategies and the need to synchronise the supply process. The company operates internal cross-functional management structures, which may be product related, and typically develop supplier networking groups.

Appendix 6: 1st Focus Group Report

- Meeting Report
- Supplier Performance Benchmarking - Focus Group Meeting

Venue:	Vauxhall UK, Luton		
Date:	4 May 1999		
Present:	Bob Soames	Procurements Development Manager	UKAEA – Contracts Group
	Ned Lawton	Manager Product Purchasing	Vauxhall Motors Limited
	Terry Davis	Supplier Development Manager	Euro Tunnel
	Roger Clark		Atomic Weapons Authority
	Brian Jeffery		Coventry University
	Carl Kochelb ergh		Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply

Objectives of Meeting

To brainstorm and explore themes relevant to supplier performance issues in order to enable the development of an industry relevant questionnaire.

Themes Explored

Objectives of transaction
Complexity of transaction
Tangible benefits
Intangible benefits
Process control
Information exchange

Findings

Objectives of Transaction

With regard to current practice within the focus group it was apparent that the broad objective of the purchasing professionals was to

establish a relationship with suppliers in order that the customers supply chain could be managed in order to bring maximum advantage to the purchaser. The current 'given' purchasing objectives were mainly based around the 'given' factors, identified as follows:

Price

Quality

Safety: Although the suppliers internal organisation's internal safety was not identified as being of prime concern

Environmental Credibility

Depth of Personnel – Including an emphasis on specific personnel

Prequalification credibility – The technical ability to supply

Capability – Historical or communicated

Financial Stability

Service Level

Potential effect on business – both for purchaser and supplier

Reliability of Supplier

Appendix 7: 2nd Focus Group Meeting Report

- Meeting Report
- Supplier Performance Benchmarking - Focus Group Meeting -2

Venue: Coventry University Business School, Coventry
Date: 14 May 1999

Present:	Samantha Stocks	Senior Purchasing Officer	Midland - HSBC
	Adrian Banks	Purchasing Manager	London Taxis International
	Les Hitchings	Interim Procurement Manager	Bank of Scotland
	Mark Piercy	Purchasing General Manager	Experian
	Brian Jeffery		Coventry University
	Carl Kochelb ergh		Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply
	Andrew Bell		Nullifire / Carboline Ltd

Objectives of Meeting

To brainstorm and explore themes relevant to supplier performance issues in order to enable the development of an industry relevant questionnaire.

Themes Explored

Objectives of transaction
Complexity of transaction
Tangible benefits
Intangible benefits
Process control
Information exchange

Findings

- 1.1 As with the earlier group it became apparent that with the services and IT sector, as with the industry and manufacturing sector that the main perceived issue with supplier / customer relationship difficulties was the 'soft' side of the relationship. This equates to how well the supplier, and also the customer are going to manage their relationship, information exchange and personal dealings with each other. The pre-transaction element was probably examined in more detail within this group, for

example the group members made use of references from previous customers outside of their own industry.

All of the group members were in accord that a usable knowledge base was required within the industry, in order to provide effective reference sites for potential purchasers. It was of course stressed that much of the relationship difficulties could be laid at the door of the customer as well as the supplier and that references would not eliminate integration issues as these could be specific to each relationship.

In assessing new suppliers many of the same tools found in manufacturing were found to be in use. The use of score based 'given' measurable factors was common, some running to many pages. Such tools are only of use with existing suppliers or suppliers with whom the customer has had an experience, providing of course that the previous relationship involved the same level of complexity as the proposed new relationship. Again what was found was that these tools could not quantify many of the listed factors without a historical perspective from which to judge, and also that the tools did not address the intangible elements that are also crucial to the relationships successful outcome, i.e. effective supply of services, goods or technology. Possible intangible factors were cited as follows:

- Supplier expectation and customer expectation of the relationship outcomes do not match.
- The supplier has little knowledge of the customers organisation only their supply requirements
- Whilst the supply technical requirements were known the other factors necessary to integration, i.e. management structures and patterns of communication were not.

-
- 1 Keith Goffin, Marek Szwajkowski, Colin New , "Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)
 - 2 C. M. Harland, "Supply chain management - relationships, chains and networks", British Journal of Management, Vol. 7, Special Issue, March 1996, pp. S63-S80.
 - 3 Karel van Donselaar; Graham Sharman, "An innovative survey in the transportation and distribution sector. (Survey Research in Operations Management)", International Journal of Operations & Production Management, July-August 1997 v17 n7-8 p707(14)
 - 4 Anita Van de Vliet, "To beat the best. (benchmarking)", Management Today, Jan 1996 p56(5),
 - 5 Doug Bartholomew, "The supply chain's value-add. (reflections on current state of supply chain management in industry)"(Editorial), Industry Week, Feb 2, 1998 v247 n3 p36(1)
 - 6 Taylor, F.W. (1911), The Principles of Scientific Management, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
 - 7 "Supply-chain management and time-based competition: the role of the supplier", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, March-April 1997 v27 n3-4 p210(16)
 - 8 Farmer, D. (1995), "Purchasing myopia - a touch of Mr Magoo", Proceedings for the First World-wide Research Symposium on Purchasing and Supply Chain Management, Arizona State University,

Phoenix, AZ, pp. 63-71.

- ⁹ John T. Landry, "Supply Chain Management." Harvard Business Review, Nov 1, 1998 p24(1),
- ¹⁰ Rick Mullin, "Knowledge management: a cultural evolution. (Dow Chemical Co)", Journal of Business Strategy, Sep-Oct 1996 v17 n5 p56(4)
- ¹¹ Paul C. Ballman, "Managing effectively in chaos, (personnel management)", Human Resource Planning, Sep 1996 v19 n3 p11(4),
- ¹² Rosabeth Moss Kanter , "Can giants dance in cyberspace? (large companies and the Internet"; Public Life; Forbes ASAP), Forbes, Dec 2, 1996 v158 n13 pS247(2),
- ¹³ Keith Goffin; Mark Szwejcowski; "Colin New, Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15),
- ¹⁴ Kolay, M.K., "Suppliers asset base - appreciating or depreciating?", International Journal of Operations & Production Management, Vol. 13 No. 8, 1993, pp. 72-86.
- ¹⁵ 7. Monczka, R.M., Callahan, T.J. and Nichols, E.L., "Predictors of relationships among buying and supplying firms", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 25 No. 10, 1995, pp. 45-59.
- ¹⁶ Ellram, L.M., "The supplier selection decision in strategic partnerships", Journal of Purchasing and Materials Management, Vol. 26 No. 4, 1990,

pp. 8-14.

- ¹⁷ 5. Leenders, M.R., Nollet, J. and Ellram, L.M., "Adapting purchasing to supply chain management", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 1, 1994, pp. 40-2.
- ¹⁸ Burt, D.N., "Managing supplies up to speed", Harvard Business Review, Vol. 67 No. 4, 1989, pp. 127-35.
- ¹⁹ Harland, C.M., "Supply chain management - relationships, chains and networks", British Journal of Management, Vol. 7, Special Issue, March 1996, pp.S63-S80.
- ²⁰ Jacky Holloway; Graham Francis; Matthew Hinton; David Mayle, "Best practice benchmarking: delivering the goods? (Proceedings of the 3rd World Congress for Total Quality Management Business Excellence Through Quality Culture)", Total Quality Management, July 1998 v9 n4-5 pS121(5)
- ²¹ "First find your bench ", The Economist, May 11, 1991 v319 n7706 p72(1).
- ²² Mzamo P. Mangaliso, "The strategic usefulness of management information as perceived by middle managers", Journal of Management, Summer 1995 v21 n2 p231(20),
- ²³ Proctor, R.A. (1991). "Marketing information systems". Management Decision, 29(4): 55-60.
- ²⁴ Christian Cull, "Let's talk about us. (Tesco PLC, relationship with its suppliers)(The Grocer focus on Tesco supplement.)", Grocer, Sep 20, 1997 v220 n7323 pS12(2),

-
- ²⁵ Keith Goffin; Marek Szwejcowski; Colin New, "Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)
- ²⁶ Mohanty, R.P. and Deshmukh, S.G., "Use of analytic hierarchic process for evaluating sources of supply", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics, Vol. 23 No. 3, 1993, pp. 22-8.
- ²⁷ Lee, H. and Wellan, D.M., "Vendor survey plan: a selection strategy for JIT/TQM Suppliers", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 23 No. 7, 1993, pp. 39-45.
- ²⁸ Larson, P.D., "Buyer-supplier co-operation, product quality and total costs", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 6, 1994, pp. 4-9.
- ²⁹ Harrison, A., "Co-makership as an extension of quality care", International Journal Quality & Reliability Management, Vol. 7 No. 2, 1990, pp. 15-22.
- ³⁰ Mohanty, R.P. and Deshmukh, S.G., "Use of analytic hierarchic process for evaluating sources of supply", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics, Vol. 23 No. 3, 1993, pp. 22-8.
- ³¹ Levy, P., Bessant, J., Sang, B. and Lamming, R., "Developing integration through total quality supply chain management", Integrated Manufacturing Systems. Vol. 6 No. 3, 1995, pp. 4-12.
- ³² Larson, P.D., "Buyer-supplier co-operation, product quality and total costs", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 6, 1994, pp. 4-9.

-
- 33 Larson, P.D., "Buyer-supplier co-operation, product quality and total costs", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 24 No. 6, 1994, pp. 4-9.
- 34 Harrison, A., "Co-makership as an extension of quality care", International Journal Quality & Reliability Management, Vol. 7 No. 2, 1990, pp. 15-22.
- 35 Turnbull, P., Delridge, R, Oliver, N. and Wilkinson, B., "Winners and losers - the 'tiering' of component suppliers in the UK automotive industry", Journal of General Management. Vol. 19 No. 1, 1993, pp. 48-63.
- 36 Merlyn, V. and Parkinson, J. (1994), *Development Effectiveness: Strategies for IS Organisational Transition*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY.
- 37 Monica Parzinger; Narender Ramarapu; E. Timmerman, "A stage-wise application of total quality management through the product life cycle" Industrial Management & Data Systems, March-April 1997 v97 n3-4 p125(6)
- 38 Powell, T.C. (1995), "Total quality management as competitive advantage: a review and empirical study", Strategic Management Journal, Vol. 16, pp. 15-37.
- 39 Stan Glaser, "Management duckspeak. (meaningless terms used in management)", Management Decision, Sept-Oct 1997 v35 n9-10 p649(3)
- 40 Nick Rich; Peter Hines, "Supply-chain management and time-based competition: the role of the supplier association", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, March-April 1997 v27

n3-4 p210(16)

- 41 Stevens, G. (1989), "Integrating the supply chain", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Materials Management, Vol. 19 No. 8, pp. 3-8.
- 42 Allan A. Gibb, "Small firms' training and competitiveness. Building upon the small business as a learning organisation", International Small Business Journal, April-June 1997 v15 n3 p13(17)
- 43 Nick Rich; Peter Hines, "Supply-chain management and time-based competition: the role of the supplier association", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, March-April 1997 v27 n3-4 p210(16)
- 44 James A.; Knill Tompkins Bernie; Andel Tom, "Time To Rise Above Supply Chain Management.", Transportation & Distribution, Oct 1, 1998 pSC16
- 45 Takeuchi, H. and Nonaka, I., "The new new product development game", Harvard Business Review, Vol. 64 No. 1, January-February 1986, pp. 137-46.
- 46 Stratford Sherman, Hot products from hot tubs, or how managers innovate. Hirotaka Takeuchi, author of 'The Knowledge-Creating Company: How Japanese Companies Create the Dynamics of Innovation')(Interview), Fortune, April 29, 1996 v133 n8 p165(3)
- 47 Allan A. Gibb, "Small firms' training and competitiveness. Building upon the small business as a learning organisation", International Small Business Journal, April-June 1997 v15 n3 p13(17)

-
- 48 Robert J. Trent, "Understanding and evaluating cross-functional sourcing team leadership", International Journal of Purchasing and Materials Management, Fall 1996 v32 n4 p29(8)
- 49 R. Likert, *New Patterns of Management* (New York McGraw-Hill, 1961), p. 162.
- 50 Mzamo P. Mangaliso, "The strategic usefulness of management information as perceived by middle managers", Journal of Management, Summer 1995 v21 n2 p231(20)
- 51 Keith Goffin; Marek Szwejczewski; Colin New, "Managing suppliers: when fewer can mean more", International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, July-August 1997 v27 n7-8 p422(15)
- 52 Harland, C.M., "Supply chain management - relationships, chains and networks", British Journal of Management, Vol. 7, Special Issue, March 1996, pp. S63-S80.
- 53 Karel van Donselaar; Graham Sharman, "An innovative survey in the transportation and distribution sector. (Survey Research in Operations Management) ", International Journal of Operations & Production Management, July-August 1997 v17 n7-8 p707(14)